

Preliminary Data Management Plan and Ethic handbook. / D1.2

WP 1, Task 1.3

Authors: Alba Matamoros (KVC), Cristina Vera (KVC), Maite Ferrando (KVC)

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Technical references

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1. List of Abbreviations

- AI - Artificial Intelligence
- AMR - Antimicrobial Resistance
- ANIPH - Avoiding the Negative Impacts produced by Plastic materials in Humanitarian contexts
- ASTM - American Society for Testing and Materials
- AUA - GEOPONIKO PANEPISTIMION ATHINO
- BBpP - Biobased and biodegradable plastics products
- CC BY - Creative Commons Attribution International Public Licence
- CC BY-NC - Creative Commons Non-Commercial License
- CC BY-ND - Creative Commons No Derivatives License
- CETEC - ASOCIACION EMPRESARIAL DE INVESTIGACION CENTRO TECNOLOGICO DEL CALZADOY DEL PLASTICO DE LA REGION DE MURCIA
- DBP - Dibutyl Phthalate
- DEHP - Di(2-ethylhexyl) Phthalate
- DMP - Data Management Plan
- DOI - Digital Object Identifier
- DPA - Data Protection Authorities
- ECHA - European Chemicals Agency
- EDPB - European Data Protection Board
- EOSC - European Open Science Cloud
- FAIR - Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
- GA - Grant Agreement
- GDPR - General Data Protection Regulation
- GLP - Good Laboratory Practice
- HTTPS - HyperText Transfer Protocol Secure
- ICT - Information and Communication Technology
- ICONS - FONDAZIONE ICONS
- IEC - Independent Ethics Committee
- ILS - Integrated Library System
- IPR - Intellectual Property Rights
- IRB - Institutional Review Board
- ISO - International Organization for Standardization
- KCB - Knowledge Centre for Bioeconomy
- KVC – Knowledge Value Consulting
- LCA - Life Cycle Assessment
- LCC - Life Cycle Costing
- MDR - Multidrug-Resistant Bacteria
- MIME - Multipurpose Internet Mail Extensions
- OECD - Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
- OIA-PMH - Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting
- OS - Open Science
- PHA - Polyhydroxyalkanoates
- PHBV - Poly(3-hydroxybutyrate-co-3-hydroxyvalerate)

- PHN - 3-hydroxynonanoic acid)
- PMS - Post Market Surveillance
- RRI - Responsible Research and Innovation
- SFTP - Secure File Transfer Protocol
- s-LCA - Social Life Cycle Assessment
- SSbD - Safe and Sustainable by Design
- T&E - Transparency and Explainability

2. Executive Summary

The ANIPH project seeks to establish an innovative polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) value chain for producing biodegradable wound dressings and recyclable water barrier packaging that degrade safely across all relevant environments. This ambitious initiative integrates cutting-edge AI predictive tools and digital traceability systems with comprehensive biological testing and public engagement strategies to ensure sustainable and effective product development.

This deliverable (D.1.2.) represents the *Preliminary Data Management Plan and Ethics Handbook*, forming part of a structured three-phase approach within Work Packages 1 and 7 (Tasks 1.3 and 7.3). It will be followed by an *Interim Data Management Plan (D.1.3.)* and culminate in the *Final Data Management Plan and Ethics Handbook (D.7.1.)*, ensuring continuous refinement of data governance throughout the project lifecycle.

The Data Management Plan addresses the complete data lifecycle from initial generation and collection through long-term preservation, implementing FAIR principles to maximise data findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability. Robust data security frameworks ensure GDPR compliance through technical safeguards including encryption protocols and stringent access controls. Ethical considerations receive extensive treatment, encompassing research integrity standards, Responsible Research Innovation (RRI) principles, AI ethics aligned with EU regulatory requirements, and specialised protocols for human tissue research. The plan establishes clear resource allocation frameworks, defines organisational responsibilities, and implements comprehensive protocols for data breach management and ongoing ethical monitoring.

3. Data Generation and Collection

In the context of ANIPH technical research project, it is crucial to emphasise that the collection and processing of personal data are not inherent to the project's primary objectives. The project predominantly involves technical aspects, and personal data is not deemed essential for most of its duration. In the pursuit of our technical research project, the data and results anticipated are of a technical nature, with the essence of our investigation revolving around acquiring, analysing, and interpreting information derived from experimental processes, scientific observations, and other technical methodologies.

The ANIPH technical research project focuses primarily on generating and collecting scientific and technical data related to PHA polymers and products. The project will also make use of pre-existing data sources when relevant, particularly to accelerate AI model development and avoid redundant experiments. Throughout the project's lifespan, our commitment lies in treating the obtained data with methodical rigour and adhering to established standards and protocols.

Personal data processing will only occur during specific public engagement activities outlined in tasks 6.3 and 12.2, as detailed in *D6.5 Public Engagement* and *D6.6 Public Engagement Strategy and Actions*. In these limited cases, informed consent forms will be required for non-professional participants involved in surveys and public events, with all personal data handled in compliance with GDPR requirements.

The consortium commits to implementing appropriate measures to ensure the security and confidentiality of any personal data that may be encountered in the later phases of the project, aligning with ethical considerations and legal requirements.

Within the data generation and collection scope, ANIPH will develop advanced digital solutions that both **utilise and produce data**. These include AI-based predictive models for PHA polymer properties, ecotoxicity profiles, and biodegradation pathways. The project's data collection efforts support an integrated ICT platform with three specialised tools:

1. A Traceability tool for secure data transfer across the value chain
2. An Evaluation & Decision tool processing collected data to support Safe and Sustainable by Design decisions
3. A Public tool communicating verified data to stakeholders

In addition, the Project must define **long-term sustainability conditions**. To this end, the repository management model must be guided by the following principles:

- Sustainability of ANIPH Repository as such
- Promoting sustainability by design.
- Promoting sustainability by synergies with other Repositories.
- Defining methodologies and protocols to ensure the re-use of the data stored in the repository.

The ANIPH Data Repository will process personal data in a GDPR compliant manner. The data obtained from public participants will be anonymised in accordance with GDPR and the European Data Protection Board (EDPB) and Data Protection Authorities (DPAs) Guidelines.

3.1. Data types and sources

The ANIPH project will **generate and collect** various types of data from multiple sources:

Technical data:
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Experimental laboratory data on PHA polymer properties - Experimental laboratory data on materials including additives, adhesives, coatings and probiotics cellulose - Molecular structure data and descriptors - Biodegradation test results and measurements - Ecotoxicity assessment data - Materials characterisation data - Spectroscopic and analytical data
Existing data:
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Desk research for: ILSs, policy/ regulations, social assessment, LCA, LCC, s-LCA - Business plan development data - Data libraries from previous related research - Public databases containing relevant polymers information - Scientific literature and published datasets
Observational and self-reported:
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Anonymised/pseudo-anonymised data from quantitative surveys - Questionnaires and qualitative interventions - Meetings/stakeholder's feedback - Material & product inspection data - Data from communication and dissemination activities - User testing results of developed tools

The origin of the data will primarily be:

- Laboratory experiments conducted by project partners
- Computational modelling and simulations
- Public engagement activities with stakeholders and citizens
- Existing scientific literature and databases (for re-use)
- Regulatory and policy documents relevant to PHA polymers

3.2. Data collection methodologies

The ANIPH project will employ various methodologies to collect data throughout its lifecycle, organized into distinct categories to ensure comprehensive coverage while maintaining clear data governance:

Administrative Data Collection:

- Partner administrative information (contact details, organisational data)
- Financial and project management data
- Email communications and meeting records
- Event registration data (including dietary requirements for General Assemblies)
- Contractual and legal documentation
- Project deliverables and reports

Laboratory-based data collection:

- Standardised biodegradation testing protocols (e.g., ISO 14851, ISO 14852)
- High-throughput screening methodologies for material characterisation
- Spectroscopic and chromatographic analytical techniques
- Computational chemistry and molecular modelling
- Formulation development data and testing results

Partners' Technical Data:

- Technical deliverables and scientific outputs
- Proprietary formulation information and methodologies
- Laboratory test results and analytical data
- Research protocols and experimental procedures
- Quality control and validation data

Software Tools and Digital Platforms:

- AI and computational methods:
 - o Automated data extraction from scientific literature
 - o High-performance computing for molecular simulations
 - o Data mining from existing databases
 - o Machine learning techniques for pattern recognition and prediction
- ICT Platform data
 - o Digital traceability system data
 - o Supply chain monitoring information
 - o User interaction and platform usage analytics

Stakeholder Engagement Data Collection:

- Structured online and in-person surveys
- Focus group discussions with key stakeholders
- Semi-structured interviews with experts
- Workshop feedback collection through standardised forms
- Co-creation sessions with end-users

Regulatory and Policy Data Collection:

- Systematic review of regulatory documents
- Comparative analysis of international standards
- Policy tracking and monitoring
- Compliance documentation and assessment data

3.3. Data size and format

ANIPH datasets are various, and the format of the data collected may vary. The Consortium will give preference to open formats (e.g. csv, txt etc.), formats compatible with the use of open-source software, or at least formats that are widely accessible without significant expenses. Most of the datasets will, preferably, be produced and stored in the following formats:

- Text documents: .doc, *.rtf, *.odt or *.pdf
- Spreadsheets: .xls
- Comma separated values: .csv
- Presentation: .ppt or *.pdf

- Image of photo formats: .jpg, *.png
- Audio formats: .mp3
- Video files: .mp4

The data collected during this project is expected to vary significantly in terms of both size and quantity. Due to the dynamic nature of the project and the diversity of data sources, it is challenging to precisely estimate the volume and scope of the data at this stage. We anticipate the following additional types of data collected: laboratory analytical data, computational modeling output, AI training datasets, public engagement data and project documentation.

Subsequent revisions and iterations will allow for a more detailed specification of the data collected. We anticipate that as the project progresses and more information becomes available, we will be able to provide a clearer understanding of the data requirements, which will be included in subsequent DMP revisions.

3.4. Data utility

Data generated within the project will primarily be used by the beneficiaries to conduct the necessary activities for achieving project objectives. The use of project results, which are expected to fundamentally rely on this data, is governed by the Consortium Agreement.

Data generated that is not considered confidential or essential for commercial exploitation (including the protection of generated IPR) will be publicly disclosed via:

- Project website (public area) for reports and deliverables classified as public within the project's Grant Agreement.
- Zenodo Public Repository for raw/processed data, primarily numeric data. At a minimum, this will include the data used to produce the project's scientific publications.

The data generated by ANIPH will have significant utility beyond the project boundaries for various stakeholders:

- Academic researchers: Access to biodegradation mechanisms and molecular factors data will advance polymer science and biodegradable materials research.
- Industry and manufacturers: Data on PHA properties and biodegradation will inform product development and material selection decisions.
- Regulatory bodies: Ecotoxicity and biodegradation profiles will support the development of standards and regulations for biopolymers.
- AI developers: Curated datasets will be valuable for developing and training next-generation predictive models in materials science.
- Environmental scientists: Data on biodegradation pathways will contribute to understanding environmental impacts of polymers.
- Policy makers: Evidence-based data will inform sustainable materials policies and circular economy initiatives.

All data will be treated with methodical rigour, adhering to established standards and protocols. The project emphasises reproducibility and transparency through standardised formats and meticulous documentation, ensuring the long-term value and accessibility of ANIPH's research outputs.

Regarding personal data, anonymisation is proposed as the main strategy for ensuring data protection. The publication of any elaborated data derived from personal data will be conducted in strict accordance with all relevant data protection regulations in force.

3.5. Data repository and long-term accessibility

Repository:

Project data repository managed by the Project Coordinator, based on Google Drive and the ICT platform storage in IONOS. The open datasets/research outputs, with an assigned DOI (Digital Object Identifier) will be published in a trusted repository (e.g., Zenodo, EOSC). Moreover, ANIPH will

- i) Define and adhere to metadata standards specific to biomaterials, describing parameters and synthesis methods.
- ii) Deposit biomaterials datasets in specialized repositories such as the Materials Project, NOMAD Repository, etc,
- iii) Host open-source software tools for biomaterials research on platforms like GitHub or GitLab,

To ensure long-term data accessibility and reusability, the ANIPH Data Repository will be developed according to the following guiding principles:

- Sustainability of the ANIPH Repository infrastructure
- Promoting sustainability by design in data storage and access mechanisms
- Creating synergies with other relevant repositories in the field
- Implementing clear methodologies and protocols to facilitate data re-use

The ANIPH Data Repository will process any personal data in a GDPR-compliant manner, with public participant data properly anonymized in accordance with EDP Band DPAs Guidelines.

3.6. Quality control measures

To ensure high data quality throughout the ANIPH project, various quality control measures will be implemented across different aspects of data management. For data generation quality control, the project will follow **Good Laboratory Practice (GLP) guidelines**[1], [2], [3], maintain regular calibration of analytical instruments, and use certified reference materials where applicable. Detailed documentation of experimental protocols and replication of key experiments will be conducted to verify reproducibility and ensure consistent results.

In terms of data processing quality control, the project will employ automated data validation checks and established outlier detection and handling protocols. Version control systems will be implemented for all data processing scripts and algorithms, while peer review of analysis methodologies will be standard practice. All data transformation steps will be thoroughly documented to maintain transparency and traceability throughout the data lifecycle.

The AI and model quality control measures will include rigorous cross-validation procedures for all predictive models and continuous performance metrics tracking and reporting. Models will undergo regular evaluation against independent test datasets, with uncertainty quantification for model predictions. Explainability analysis for AI-based predictions will be conducted to ensure transparency and interpretability of results.

For survey and qualitative data quality control, all survey instruments will undergo pilot testing before deployment. Interview and focus group facilitators will be conducted by specialised personnel, and qualitative data will be independently coded by multiple researchers to minimise bias. Stakeholder verification of interpreted results will be sought, and methodological limitations will be transparently reported to maintain scientific integrity.

Documentation and reporting standards will include standardised metadata collection for all datasets and comprehensive data dictionaries. Clear documentation of data limitations and gaps will be maintained, with regular data quality reports produced throughout the project. Independent auditing of data management procedures will be conducted to ensure compliance with established standards. Technical infrastructure measures will comprise automated data backup procedures and data integrity checks using checksums.

These comprehensive quality control measures will ensure that all data generated and collected within the ANIPH project maintains the highest standards of accuracy, reliability, and reproducibility, supporting the development of trustworthy AI tools and robust research outcomes.

3.7. Data Re-use Strategy and Purpose

The ANIPH project will strategically re-use existing data to provide benchmarks for evaluations of benefits of chosen materials and manufacturing solutions, for sustainability assessments while enhancing the development of AI predictive tools for PHA polymers. This includes:

- Bibliographic data from scientific literature on polymer biodegradation
- Publicly available molecular databases containing polymer structures and properties
- Existing biodegradation test results from previous research initiatives
- Existing test results on characterisation of the polymers and materials (thermal, rheological, mechanical and barrier properties)
- Previous data on ecotoxicity regarding the chemical structure, the physicochemical properties (e.g. environmental conditions, species-specific) for model training or validation
- Previous data on additives for the toxicity predictive assessment
- Data concerning 3D printing properties, results obtained in the study of similar materials, and results obtained in the previous probiotics analysis to establish the initial study ranges.

Re-using this data establishes a robust foundation for our AI models, accelerating development timelines while conserving resources. This approach directly supports ANIPH's primary objective of developing accurate AI-based tools for predicting biodegradation properties of PHA polymers. The data generation and re-use strategy aligns with the project's goal of creating high-throughput methods that identify key molecular factors determining degradability and categorise PHA formulations based on their biodegradability profiles, their technical properties and functionality. All reused data will be obtained from publicly accessible sources or under licenses that permit reuse for scientific and non-commercial purposes. Data will be collected from reputable sources, including scholarly articles, established industry publications, and other studies of demonstrable value or reliability. Examples of such studies include previous partner research with known and approved methodologies, and publications by international organizations. When utilising pre-existing data, users will log its source and provide a clear reference. This reference will include a direct link if the source is available online, or full publishing information if an online reference is not available.

Certain datasets initially considered were ultimately discarded due to:

- Inconsistent testing methodologies
- Incomplete documentation of experimental conditions
- Outdated measurements not meeting current standards
- Incompatible data formats requiring excessive transformation

4. FAIR data

To ensure that research data can be used, shared, and re-used it is crucial to take care that those data are accessible, understandable, and usable. This requires clear data description, annotation, contextual information, and documentation explaining how data were created or digitised, what data mean or what their content and structure are.

4.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

In order to make data findable, ANIPH partners will ensure that each file of data is accompanied by a set of metadata to aid discoverability. The Consortium will adopt the following naming conventions that provides a clear version number by following time sequence (the most recent the most updated version) to make data accessible, understandable, and usable:

DATA_DELIVERABLE NUMER_FILE NAME_PROJECT NAME.FORMAT

The Consortium also will encourage establishing links between data collected and stored and the associated documentation, following recommendations such as the following:

- Including information within the data or document itself, e.g. in the document properties function of a file or the file header.
- Including information about the file's creation (when and who), size and extension.
- Keeping a database of metadata with links to files.
- Storing a readme.txt file alongside the data which provides basic explanatory details. Txt. Files will be acceptable to explain very simple stuff like how to connect to a database, not the database explanation itself.
- Recording relevant context in lab notebooks or associated papers and reports
- Including links to websites or web pages which explain the context of the research.

Metadata within Microsoft Office files is retained in the 'Properties' field associated with each file and can be adjusted in accordance with the recommendations outlined above. For alternative file formats, guidance will be sought from the respective software providers. Image metadata can be incorporated using proprietary or open-source photo editing software, or via other tools facilitating metadata modification, including file management applications.

As outlined in the previous section, all datasets published in trusted repositories (e.g. Zenodo, EOSC) will be assigned a persistent identifier (e.g. DOI), ensuring long-term traceability and citability.

Rich metadata will be provided to enable data discovery and reusability. This metadata will include title, authors, creation date, keywords, abstract/description, file format, and licensing terms. Where applicable, disciplinary metadata standards will be followed, and additional metadata specific to biomaterials (e.g., polymer composition, test conditions, degradation parameters) will be defined by the consortium.

To improve discoverability, search keywords and thematic descriptors will be included in the metadata fields. Metadata will be deposited in repositories that support harvesting and indexing (e.g., via OIA-PMH) facilitation integration into data catalogues and aggregators.

4.2. Making data accessible

Research data/outputs will be openly available, whenever possible, and as soon as possible. The access to some data (e.g. personal data, confidential knowhow) will be restricted if they compromise its commercialisation or have inadequate protection.

Each partner has the right to request access rights, background and results as specified in Article 16 of the Grant Agreement and Annex 5. Provisions for EU Commission access to restricted data for verification purposes will be granted.

Moreover, ANIPH will i) Provide open access to biomaterials datasets, either through direct download links or by hosting them on open repositories with appropriate licenses. ii): Release analysis tools and simulation software under open-source licenses, allowing researchers to access, modify, and redistribute the code freely; iii) Offer user support and documentation for software tools

Data:

Accessibility means that metadata and data are understandable to humans and machines and may be retrievable by their identifier via a standardised communication protocol. As foreseen in Article 16 of the Grant Agreement (GA), the partners must grant access to each other's information, subject to the restrictions on intellectual property and any special procedures set out in Annex 5 of the GA. The ANIPH consortium intends to make all non-confidential data openly available through trusted repositories as mentioned, in accordance with FAIR principles and EU open science policies.

However, specific datasets may remain restricted or partially closed due to legitimate interests, protection of intellectual property, or the presence of personal/sensitive information (e.g., from public engagement activities). These restrictions will be documented and justified on a case-by-case basis.

In such cases, access may be granted under controlled conditions, such as through data use agreements or request forms validated by the data provider.

If an embargo is applied, it will be temporary and justified by the need to publish results in peer-reviewed journals or to secure intellectual property protection (e.g., patent filings). Embargo periods will not exceed 6 to 12 months unless otherwise agreed by the consortium.

Data accessibility will be **further defined in the final version of this deliverables** in terms of:

- Where will the data and associated metadata, documentation and code be deposited taking into consideration that where possible preference should be given to certified repositories supporting open access.
- How will access be provided and if there would be restrictions on use.
- The authentication procedure to authorise data access.

In general, data will be accessible through free and standardised protocols (e.g., HTTPS, DOI resolution, OAI-PMH). User authentication will depend on the nature of the dataset: for open datasets, no authentication will be required; for restricted datasets, access credentials and institutional email verification may apply. The Ethics Manager (KVC) will review access conditions in case of sensitive datasets or external requests.

Dissemination of results:

The beneficiaries must disseminate their results as soon as feasible, in a publicly available format, subject to any restrictions due to the protection of intellectual property, security rules or legitimate

interests. A beneficiary that intends to disseminate its results must give at least 15 days advance notice to the other beneficiaries (unless agreed otherwise), together with sufficient information on the results it will disseminate. Any other beneficiary may object within (unless agreed otherwise) 15 days of receiving notification if it can show that its legitimate interests in relation to the results or background would be significantly harmed. In such cases, the results may not be disseminated unless appropriate steps are taken to safeguard those interests.

Open science: open access to scientific publications:

The beneficiaries must ensure open access to peer-reviewed scientific publications related to their results. In particular, they must ensure that:

- At the latest at the time of publication, a machine-readable electronic copy of the published version or the final peer-reviewed manuscript accepted for publication, is deposited in a trusted repository for scientific publications.
- Immediate open access is provided to the deposited publication via the repository, under the latest available version of the Creative Commons Attribution International Public Licence (CC BY) or a licence with equivalent rights; for monographs and other long-text formats, the licence may exclude commercial uses and derivative works (e.g. CC BY-NC, CC BY-ND), and
- Information is given via the repository about any research output, or any other tools and instruments needed to validate the conclusions of the scientific publication.

Beneficiaries (or authors) must retain sufficient intellectual property rights to comply with the open access requirements.

Metadata:

The use of common data and metadata standards are a key aspect for semantic and technological data operability. Metadata can describe the content, context, and provenance of datasets in a standardised and structured manner, typically describing the purpose, origin, temporal characteristics, geographic location, authorship, access conditions and terms of use of a dataset. This provides structured searchable information that helps users to find existing data resources, judge whether a particular dataset is suitable for their research purpose and provides a bibliographic record for citing data.

Standard dictionaries of metadata will be used for all data types produced by the data creators. Metadata will include different types and templates to gather this information:

- 1. Descriptive metadata: describe a resource for retrieval and identification. They may contain elements such as title, abstract, author, keywords, etc.**

Title	[Title of the resource]
Creator(s)	[Name(s) of the creator(s) or author(s)]
Date Created/Published	[Date when the resource was created or published]
Description	[Brief description of the resource, including its content, purpose, or significance]
Subject(s)	[Keywords or phrases that describe the topic(s) or subject(s) of the resource]
Language	[Language(s) of the resource]
Format	[Format of the resource, such as text, image, audio, video, etc.]

Extent	[Physical or digital size of the resource, duration for audio/video, number of pages for text, etc.]
Publisher	[Entity or individual responsible for making the resource available]
Rights	[Information about the copyright status or usage rights of the resource]
Identifier	[Unique identifier or URL assigned to the resource]
Source	[Information about the origin or source of the resource]
Relation	[Relationship of the resource to other resources, if applicable]
Coverage	[Geographical, temporal, or thematic coverage of the resource]
Audience	[Intended audience or target demographic for the resource]
Contributor(s)	[Names of individuals or organizations that contributed to the creation or development of the resource]
Version	[Version number or information about any revisions or updates]
Keywords	[Additional keywords or phrases relevant to the resource]

2. Structural metadata: relationships between different sets of associated data in the context of databases, such as schema describing associations between tables.

Resource Identifier	[Unique identifier for the resource]
Hierarchy	[Description of the hierarchical structure of the resource, such as chapters, sections, pages, etc.]
Sequence	[Order or sequence of the components within the resource]
Navigation	[Information about how to navigate or access different parts of the resource]
Relationships	[Information about the relationships between different components or parts of the resource]
File Format	[Format of the resource, including file extensions and MIME types]
Duration	[For multimedia resources, the duration or length of the resource]
Resolution	[For images or videos, the resolution or dimensions]
Bit Rate	[For audio or video files, the bit rate or quality]
Compression	[If applicable, information about compression methods used]
Checksums	[Checksum values to verify data integrity]
Annotations	[Information about any annotations, bookmarks, or metadata embedded within the resource]
Access Restrictions	[Any access restrictions or permissions associated with specific components or parts of the resource]
Version	[Version number or information about any revisions or updates]
Keywords	[Additional keywords or phrases relevant to the resource]

3. Administrative metadata: provides the information necessary to help process a resource.

An example might be the date of creation or how a resource was created. It may contain several subgroups of administrative information. Among the most common are metadata on rights and metadata for long-term preservation. The latter is one of the primary purposes of repositories.

Resource Identifier	[Unique identifier for the resource]
Creator(s)	[Name(s) of the creator(s) or author(s)]
Contributor(s)	[Names of individuals or organizations that contributed to the creation or development of the resource]
Creation Date	[Date when the resource was created]
Publisher	[Entity or individual responsible for making the resource available]
Publication Date	[Date when the resource was published or made available]
Modification Date	[Date when the resource was last modified or updated]
Version	[Version number or information about any revisions or updates]
Publisher	[Entity or individual responsible for making the resource available]
File Format	[Format of the resource, including file extensions and MIME types]
Size	[Size of the resource in bytes or other appropriate units]
Storage Location	[Location where the resource is stored or archived]
Access Rights	[Information about access rights or permissions associated with the resource]
Preservation Metadata	[Information about preservation strategies or metadata necessary for long-term preservation]
Rights Management	[Information about rights management or access control mechanisms]
Metadata Creation	[Details about the process of creating or capturing metadata for the resource]
Metadata Standards	[Information about the metadata standards or schemas used to describe the resource]
Checksums	[Checksum values to verify data integrity]

4.3. Making data interoperable

Interoperability is the ability to access and process machine-readable data from multiple sources, sometimes automatically, without that data losing meaning or integrity. To achieve this goal, data requires:

- Syntactic interoperability: widespread adoption of standard data formats, and the implementation of application programming interfaces and connectors that allow data from multiple sources to be accessed and integrated.
- Semantic interoperability: data and information must be exchanged across systems without its context and meaning being lost; and
- Search interoperability: it enables a user to conduct queries across two or more collections of data.

Thus, interoperability enables improved data usability and use. For this reason, putting in practice interoperability will be a priority for the Consortium to have the following benefits (among others):

- Reducing time, effort and expense spent on data collection.
- Eliminating frustration and risks associated with finding inconsistent and incomplete data.
- Making available sustainable, disaggregated data for effective decision-making.

All datasets will be described using standard descriptive metadata, such as Dublin Core and DataCite Metadata Schema to ensure metadata interoperability for indexing and discoverability. Information about experimental processes, modelling, etc. will be made available with the data used to assure the reproducibility and the validation of the project results.

Data will be available in easily accessible formats (when possible open formats will be used) such as:

- Spreadsheets (e.g., CSV, XLSX)
- Text (TXT, DOCX, RTF)
- Machine readable formats (HDF5, JSON, XML, HTML)

Moreover, ANIPH will:

- i) Ensure compatibility and integration with existing biomaterials databases, computational tools, and simulation platforms
- ii) Design software with well-defined APIs and user interfaces to enable interoperability with other biomaterials research tools/platforms Explore the use of controlled vocabularies to support consistent annotation of PHA-related data. Utilise standard data exchange protocols to facilitate seamless data transfer between different components of the project's ICT infrastructure

To enhance interoperability specifically for AI-based tools, the project will:

- Document data transformation pipelines to ensure reproducibility
- Provide clear documentation of data models and algorithms
- Use standardised formats for molecular descriptors and polymer properties
- Implement FAIR Digital Objects approaches where appropriate

These measures will ensure that data generated within ANIPH can be effectively combined with external datasets and integrated into existing research ecosystems in the fields of biodegradable materials, polymer science, and sustainable materials development.

Considering the international nature of the consortium, English will be used for all published and internally shared data. In case data is generated in different languages (i.e. interviews with local stakeholders), English transcripts or translations shall be made available.

4.4. Increase data re-use

The obtained data by developing the project could be made openly accessible if the General Assembly (GA) agrees to. The main aim is to make the data openly accessible for as long as possible. The decision on the long-term availability of the data collected and processed in the framework of the ANIPH project will be taken as the data are stored.

After the completion of each task involving data collection, the data will be made openly accessible when the following requirements are met:

- Data collection and processing are completed.
- Data checking - in terms of quality control - is performed.
- The exploitation plan of the consortium partners, both in terms of scientific publications and commercial purposes, is finalised.

ANIPH will share the collected data sets available under a CC BY NC, unless otherwise indicated, allowing the sharing and reuse of the data by stakeholders with knowledge of the legal criteria on the ownership and the use that can be made of them. Partners must provide information about tools needed for validating the results, according to protection agreements, confidentiality and ethics.

Moreover, ANIPH will

- (i) Maintain version control for biomaterials datasets and software repositories using versioning systems like Git.
- (ii) Implement quality assurance measures including data validation, error correction, and documentation of experimental protocols.
- (iii) Foster a community around biomaterials datasets and software tools by encouraging collaboration, feedback, and contributions from researchers and developers, thereby enhancing their reusability and impact.

Each partner generating data will be responsible for its quality, covering both internally shared and published data. This responsibility extends to the data's content (e.g., ensuring data originates from tests run under valid conditions, maintaining accuracy) and formal aspects (e.g., correct formatting, removal of outliers from numerical data, appropriate metadata, consistent internal referencing, correct use of data representations like pictures within project reports).

Data intended for publication must meet the specific requirements outlined in this document (e.g., defined metadata standards, specified file formats). The Data Management & Ethics Manager, the Technical Manager, will work together with the Project Coordinator to review the overall data quality and ensure its coherence with the requirements of the latest version of the Data Management Plan. They will collaborate with the data owner to address any identified shortcomings. Published data is generally intended for reuse and will be deposited in the Zenodo repository for a minimum of three years, unless otherwise specified. It is acknowledged that some data may, in any case, become obsolete within a shorter period.

5. Other research outputs

The management of other research outputs potentially generated or reused within the project (e.g., software, models, new materials) will be discussed. When relevant, their compliance with the FAIR principles will be detailed.

5.1. Software And Algorithms

- **AI predictive models:** Machine learning models will be trained on curated datasets to predict key performance indicators such as biodegradation rates, ecotoxicity, and physicochemical properties of PHAs.
- **Computational models and simulations:** Quantum chemical and molecular dynamics models will be used to explore the behaviour of PHA materials at the molecular level, including crystallinity and degradation pathways.
- **ICT platform's Evaluation & Decision tool (KPI10)** which will support SSbD decision-making and composed by: (1) Traceability Tool to capture (by QR code), store (by cloud), process (by ICT devices) and communicate information securely (by a public blockchain) across ANIPH value chain; (2) Evaluation & Decision Tool: It will integrate the evaluation matrix and scoring system as defined in the SSbD and social readiness evaluation framework. This tool will enable the assessment of the different results and options helping the decision-making process based on safety and sustainability criteria; (3) Public Tool to communicate public reliable information about the ANIPH value chain and its impacts.

5.2. Models And Protocols

The ANIPH project will generate a diverse set of models and experimental protocols that underpin the project's scientific advancements, particularly in the development and assessment of biobased and biodegradable plastic products (BBpPs). These models and protocols play a central role in supporting the predictability, reproducibility, and validation of the project's outcomes across laboratory, computational, and real-environment conditions.

Types of models developed:

- **Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD) decision models:** These conceptual models will operationalise sustainability and safety criteria into the material and process selection logic, enabling the comparison of design alternatives based on technical, environmental, economic and social indicators. They will be fully integrated within the ICT platform and informed by results from LCA, s-LCA and LCC models.
- **Life Cycle Assessment (LCA and s-LCA) models:** Developed in accordance with ISO 14040/14044 standards, these models will evaluate the environmental and social impacts of materials and processes throughout the BBpP value chain.
- **Life Cycle Costing (LCC) models:** These models will assess the economic performance of products and processes, providing input for the comparison of alternatives under the Safe and Sustainable by Design framework.

Experimental and operational protocols

- **Biodegradation testing protocols:** Standardised methodologies will be applied and adapted from ISO 14851, ISO 14855-2, ASTM D6691 and UNI 11462 covering 3-tier testing approach across soil, freshwater, and marine environments.
- **Ecotoxicity assessment protocols:** Based on the OECD 207 guidelines and ISO Standards 18763, these will assess acute and chronic effects of ANIPH materials on selected organisms. Parameters include survival, growth, reproduction, and biochemical endpoints.
- **PHA production protocols:** Standard procedures for the fermentative synthesis and extraction of PHBV and PHN polymers will be developed, addressing key variables such as feedstock composition, microbial strain performance and crystallinity control.
- **Formulation and compounding protocols:** they will detail the incorporation of biobased and biodegradable additives to modulate thermal, mechanical and biodegradation properties of the compounds.
- **Manufacturing protocols:** they will be established for cast/blown extrusion, 3D printing, and spray-coating techniques, including surface-to-volume ratio control and compatibility with wound dressing and packaging applications.
- **Laboratory testing protocols: procedures to validate the mechanical and biological properties of the polymers, compounds, materials and final products.** All relevant stages will include technical validation of the material properties, such as mechanical strength, permeability, rheology, thermal behaviour, biodegradation performance, cytotoxicity, biocompatibility, and antibacterial activity to ensure their suitability for intended end uses. Final products (e.g., wound dressing and flexible packaging prototypes) will also be validated under application-relevant conditions to assess performance, functionality, and compliance with target specifications.
- **Model validation protocols:** AI models and computational simulations will follow defined procedures for dataset curation, preprocessing, training, cross-validation, performance reporting, and uncertainty analysis. Model development and validation will be supported by the project's digital assets, including the AI-based predictive system and the ANIPH ICT platform. Transparent documentation of these processes will ensure replicability and compliance with trustworthiness principles.

5.3. Publications And Dissemination

In addition to the above-described data, the ANIPH Consortium envisages the development of internal databases (such as stakeholder databases including organizations that could have interests and impacts on the project results) derived from the communication and dissemination activities to be executed throughout the project. Such databases are to provide an overview of stakeholders' relevant information (e.g. names and institutional email addresses), information on the newsletter subscribers, and data on registration to events via the project website. In addition, other types of data (such as subscribers to the project newsletter or online users' navigation data) will be collected from the ANIPH website and other platform's analytics (like LinkedIn and YouTube) and monitoring tools (Matomo), however including no sensitive data and in line with the Privacy Notice published on the website (<https://aniph.eu/privacy-notice/>).

When filming for the production of specific audiovisual materials (such as, video interviews), a dedicated Consent Form, in line with GDPR, will be provided for signature of the interviewee to allow ANIPH consortium to use the filmed footage and video statements for the purposes of public communication activities and for publications on various communication channels (such as, ANIPH's website and social media).

This information will be available only to the Consortium (thus, it will not be reused nor published on open access repositories - such as Zenodo) and will be stored in the selected platforms available to project partners for internal use, which ensure the secure archiving of data (see previous sections of the report).

6. Allocation of resources

6.1. Costs

Costs related to open access to research data in the Horizon Europe programme are eligible costs (article 6.2. C Costs of Purchase) under the conditions defined in the HE Grant Agreement.

6.2. Responsibilities

Implementing the specifications of the Data Management Plan (DMP) retrospectively could be time-consuming. Therefore, the Consortium policy is to apply the DMP from the data gathering phase onwards. As each partner is responsible for gathering and generating data, they are also accountable for complying with the DMP requirements.

The partner KVC as a Data Management and Ethics Manager as described in the Consortium Agreement is the responsible of update the Data Management Plan according to the schedule of deliverables set within the Grant Agreement.

KVC, together the partner ICONS, as Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Manager, AUA as Technical Manager will be actively supporting the Consortium in identifying candidate data for publication. Jointly, the Project Coordinator (CETEC) and the Exploitation Manager (ICONS) will ensure that data designated for publication does not compromise the protection of Intellectual Property Rights (IPR). This involves consultation with Work Package Leaders and involved partners. AUA will contribute to this process by focusing on aspects relevant to preserving the novelty of any publication under preparation.

ICONS in collaboration with the Project Coordinator will manage the Zenodo community created for ANIPH.

Data management in ANIPH follows a shared responsibility model. All partners are jointly responsible for ensuring that the collection, processing, and sharing of data comply with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and other applicable legal and ethical requirements. This includes implementing appropriate technical and organisational measures to ensure data protection, accountability, and traceability throughout the project lifecycle.

- **CETEC**, as project coordinator, oversees the overall implementation of the Data Management Plan (DMP) and ensures alignment with the work plan, risk management procedures, and the exploitation strategy.
- **KVC**, leader of Task 1.3, develops and maintains the ethics framework, monitors compliance with data protection obligations, and provides guidance on privacy, consent, and research integrity.
- **ICONS** is responsible for supporting partners in publishing research outputs in open-access repositories (e.g. Zenodo), applying FAIR principles, and ensuring proper licensing and metadata standards.

- **Each partner** is considered a joint controller for the data they generate or manage and must integrate data protection and documentation practices into their daily activities. Where relevant, partners will appoint internal data contacts or advisors to ensure adherence to GDPR requirements.

7. Data security

In the following sections information about data protection and the technical security measures is presented.

7.1. Data protection: Compliance with GDPR

This Data Management Plan outlines our commitment to ensuring compliance with applicable international and national regulations, particularly the European Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), throughout the duration of the project. While the processing of personal data is not extensive, it may occur primarily during the implementation of work packages 6 *Communication, dissemination and exploitation baselines* & 12 *Communication, dissemination, exploitation and capacity building-booster*. We aim to uphold the principles of data protection and privacy in all project activities. Data collected through the ANIPH website will be handled in line with the Privacy Notice available on the website: <https://aniph.eu/privacy-notice/>

7.1.1. Purpose

The project underscores the minimisation and limitation of personal data processing. Though personal data processing is minimal during the research phase, it may be necessary to process data for disseminating project results, such as events, training, and publicity activities. Any personal data processed will be strictly necessary for the intended purpose and handled in accordance with GDPR principles.

7.1.2. Accuracy

Acknowledging the significance of data accuracy in GDPR compliance, measures will be implemented to ensure that any personal data collected or processed is accurate, relevant, and up to date throughout the project lifecycle. Routine reviews and updates will be conducted to maintain data accuracy.

7.1.3. Integrity and confidentiality

Upholding the integrity and confidentiality of personal data is paramount. All personal data collected or processed will be treated with the utmost confidentiality, and security measures will be implemented to prevent unauthorised access, disclosure, or alteration. Encryption, access controls, and secure storage mechanisms will be employed to safeguard personal data.

7.1.4. Accountability

Maintaining accountability in data processing activities is paramount. Clear roles and responsibilities will be assigned to project team members to ensure compliance with GDPR obligations. Regular audits and assessments will be conducted to monitor compliance and address any issues that may arise.

7.1.5. Personal information

Any personal information collected will be processed lawfully, fairly, and transparently in accordance with GDPR requirements. Individuals will be informed of the purpose and legal basis for processing their personal data, and their rights regarding their data will be respected at all times.

7.1.6. Anonymisation and pseudoanonymisation

Where feasible, personal data will be anonymised or pseudonymised to minimise risks to data subjects. Anonymisation and pseudonymisation techniques will be employed to irreversibly dissociate personal data from individual identities, thereby reducing the likelihood of re-identification

7.1.7. Informed consent procedures

Where necessary, informed consent will be obtained from data subjects prior to the processing of their personal data. Clear and comprehensible information will be provided to individuals regarding the purposes of data processing, their rights, and how their data will be used. Consent will be freely given, specific, informed, and revocable at any time (see a template in Annex A of this deliverable).

7.1.8. Incidental findings

ANIPH will establish protocols for managing incidental findings that may arise during project activities, ensuring appropriate handling of unexpected discoveries through defined reporting mechanisms, ethical review processes, and communication strategies while maintaining clear limitations on researchers' obligations and protecting data subject rights throughout the discovery and disclosure process.

7.1.9. International data transfer

This section addresses the project's compliance with ethical, legal, and data security requirements, with a special focus on the transfer of data to a collaborating partner located outside the European Union.

All personal data collected and processed within the project will follow the principles of lawfulness, fairness, transparency, purpose limitation, data minimisation, accuracy, storage limitation, integrity, and confidentiality.¹

A part of the project's collaboration involves the transfer of data to the partner **TVB**, located in **Canada**. This transfer is conducted in full compliance with European regulations, as detailed below.

Legal Basis for the Transfer

The transfer of personal data from the EU to Canada is based on the European Commission's **Adequacy Decision** (Decision 2002/2/EC, re-affirmed in January 2024). This decision establishes that Canada's private-sector data protection law, the *Personal Information Protection and Electronic Documents Act (PIPEDA)*, provides a level of protection for personal data that is "essentially equivalent" to that guaranteed within the European Union.

Therefore, the transfer of data to Canadian entities subject to PIPEDA does not require additional safeguards such as Standard Contractual Clauses (SCCs).

Applicability to the Project Partner (TVB)

The Adequacy Decision applies specifically to **private-sector organisations in Canada** operating in a commercial capacity. Based on the description of the partner TVB and its role in the project (development of bio-based adhesives and barrier coatings), it is concluded that **TVB is a commercial entity** and, consequently, is subject to the obligations of PIPEDA. The project will formally verify this status with the partner.

Types of Data to be Transferred and Minimisation

To comply with the principle of data minimisation, a clear distinction is made between research data (non-personal) and the personal data strictly necessary for the collaboration:

1. **Research Data (Non-Personal):** This constitutes the bulk of the data to be transferred. It includes anonymised technical and scientific data that does not allow for the identification of individuals.
Examples: Experimental results on adhesives, polymerisation data, spectroscopic measurements, chemical formulations, performance metrics of coatings.
2. **Personal Data (Limited):** A minimal set of personal data will be transferred, solely for project management, communication, and proper work attribution.
Examples: Name, institutional affiliation, professional email address, and project role of the researchers and technical staff involved.
Purpose: The transfer of this data is essential for coordinating tasks, holding meetings, managing access to shared platforms, and ensuring correct authorship in publications and results.

Contingency Plan

In the unlikely event that it is determined that the partner TVB is not covered by PIPEDA, the project will activate an alternative transfer mechanism. **Standard Contractual Clauses (SCCs)**, as adopted by the European Commission, would be signed between the project coordinator (data exporter) and TVB (data importer) before any transfer takes place.

7.2. Technical security measures

Robust technical measures will be implemented across the ANIPH project to safeguard research data, prevent unauthorized access, and ensure the integrity, confidentiality and availability of digital assets. These measures support compliance with GDPR requirements (Article 15 of the Grant Agreement) and are aligned with best practices in secure research data management.

Each partner generating data is responsible for ensuring that their data (whether raw or elaborated from data provided by other partners) is regularly backed up and stored safely, in accordance with internal security procedures. Should such data also be shared internally within the Consortium, the data owner shall further be responsible for the methods employed for information exchange.

In addition, where data is shared among all Consortium members through public cloud facilities, such as Google Drive, the Coordinator shall be tasked with conducting regular backups of the complete shared repository. The frequency of these backups will be determined by the level of activity on the data, anticipated to be, for instance, once or twice per month. These backups are intended to mitigate the risk of accidental data loss.

7.2.1. Access controls

Access to project data, models, and computational tools will be managed through role-based access permissions. Only authorised personnel from partner organisations will be granted access to datasets and system based on their involvement in specific work packages and tasks.

Each data repository or digital platform (e.g., the internal cloud system, the ANIPH ICT platform) will implement the following:

- User authentication via strong passwords or institutional credentials
- Differentiated access levels (read, write, admin) based on roles and modular architecture
- Logging of access activity and audit trails, especially for sensitive or restricted data
- Immediate deactivation of access upon staff departure or change of responsibilities

These controls will be regularly reviewed by the data management lead at each partner, coordinated under WP1.

7.2.2. Encryption standards

All personal or confidential data stored or transferred within ANIPH systems will be protected using strong encryption mechanisms, particularly in the rare cases where sensitive data (e.g., survey responses from public engagement tasks) are collected.

- **At-rest encryption:** All data stored on project servers, including in cloud storage (e.g., internal partner systems), will be encrypted at rest using strong, industry-standard encryption protocols.
- **In-transit encryption:** Data exchanges across partners or external platforms will use secure protocols such as HTTPS, SFTP, or encrypted email for document exchange.
- Cryptographic keys will be managed securely and will not be embedded in source code or shared via unsecured channels.

No personal data will be stored or unencrypted mobile devices external hard drives, or USB keys without prior authorisation and encryption.

7.2.3. Backup procedures

To prevent data loss and ensure business continuity, the following backup strategies will be applied:

- Automated daily backups of project files and datasets will be implemented in primary cloud-based environments (e.g. IONOS servers and internal repositories at each partner)
- Versioned backups will be maintained with retention policies (minimum 30 days) to allow recovery in case of accidental deletions or corruption.
- Critical project repositories (e.g. AI model datasets, versioned protocols, deliverables) will be synchronised across redundant storage locations.
- Periodic tests of backup recovery processes will be carried out to verify the integrity and accessibility of stored data.

These backup procedures are critical to fulfilling the obligations under Article 20 of the Grant Agreement, which requires the consortium to preserve records for five years after the final payment.

7.3. Data breach protocols

In the unlikely event of a data breach affecting personal, confidential or sensitive data within the ANIPH project, a structured response protocol will be activated to contain the incident, assess its impact, and notify the appropriate stakeholders. This protocol ensures compliance with Article 15 of the Grant Agreement and the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), in particular Articles 33 and 34.

7.3.1. Breach identification and reporting

All consortium partners are required to immediately report any suspected or confirmed data breach to the person responsible for data management at their organisation. The report must include:

- A description of the nature of the breach
- The categories and approximate number of data subjects and records affected
- The potential impact on data subjects or project integrity
- Any actions already taken to contain or mitigate the breach

Initial reporting should occur within 24 hours of detection.

7.3.2. Containment and mitigation

Upon notification, the affected partner(s) must immediately take technical and procedural actions to stop the breach and limit its impact. These actions may include:

- Disabling compromised user accounts or access points
- Restoring data from backups if applicable
- Notifying relevant IT or legal departments
- Engaging external support if necessary (e.g., cybersecurity firms)

The Data Management Team (under WP1) will coordinate a centralised response and ensure consistency across the consortium.

7.3.3. Notification to authorities and individuals

If the breach involves personal data and is likely to result in a risk to the rights and freedoms of individuals, the responsible organisation must notify its national Data Protection Authority within 72 hours, in accordance with GDPR Article 33.

When the breach poses a high risk to affected individuals, those individuals must also be informed without undue delay (Article 34 GDPR), unless appropriate technical protection measures (e.g. encryption) rendered the data unintelligible.

7.3.4. Documentation and follow-up

All breaches, regardless of severity, will be documented in an internal incident register that includes:

- Date and time of breach detection and notification
- Description of the breach and affected systems
- Mitigation measures applied and their effectiveness
- Decision on whether notification was required
- Lessons learned and corrective actions to prevent recurrence

This documentation will be retained in compliance with Article 20 of the Grant Agreement for audit purposes.

8. Ethics: Project overview and key ethical challenges

In line with the EU's commitment to responsible and ethical research practices, the ANIPH project places ethics at the core of its innovation process. This comprehensive ethical framework addresses the complex challenges inherent in developing biobased solutions for humanitarian contexts, where considerations of human dignity, environmental sustainability, and social justice intersect. This section outlines our commitment to upholding the highest ethical standards throughout the project lifecycle, ensuring that technological advancement serves the greater good while respecting individual rights, cultural values, and environmental integrity.

8.1. Research integrity

Research integrity forms the foundation of ANIPH's scientific endeavour, ensuring that all research activities meet the highest standards of rigour, honesty, and transparency. The project upholds ethical principles through systematic prevention of research misconduct, including falsification, fabrication, or plagiarism, via clear protocols for data collection, verification, and documentation. Under the guidance of an external ethics advisor, all consortium members implement robust conflict of interest management systems, with mandatory disclosure requirements and independent review mechanisms to maintain objectivity throughout the research process. These measures, combined with regular audits and adherence to international research standards, foster a culture of accountability that strengthens public trust in scientific outcomes while safeguarding the credibility of innovations intended for humanitarian applications.

8.1.1. Human health and PHA wound healing: ethical and scientific-technical considerations

ANIPH addresses complex ethical challenges regarding PHA in contact with human tissues, particularly for medical applications. These considerations include biocompatibility, absence of antibiotics in humanitarian contexts, environmental sustainability, and additive exposure risks. Four key areas require ongoing assessment:

1. **PHA in contact with human tissue:** PHAs demonstrate good biocompatibility with minimal cytotoxicity. However, crystallinity variations affect degradation rates, requiring careful balance between stability and biodegradability.
2. **Absence of antibiotics in wound dressings:** While PHA dressings without antibiotics align with antimicrobial stewardship principles, the high infection risk in conflict zones raises ethical questions about standard of care provision.
3. **Environmental sustainability:** PHA's biodegradability offers significant advantages in humanitarian contexts where waste management is challenging, reducing environmental burden while supporting sustainable development goals.
4. **Additive exposure and health effects:** Comprehensive safety assessment includes evaluating potential risks from plasticizers, reinforcement agents, and other processing additives used in PHA formulations.

All health-related risks will be addressed through rigorous testing protocols, transparent stakeholder communication, and robust post-market surveillance systems to ensure patient safety while advancing sustainable humanitarian healthcare solutions.

8.2. Open science and ethics

The Open Access to research data and the free availability of research outputs will be guaranteed and maximised whilst considering the Ethics and the Data Management Plan-DMP. Research results will be openly published and at the disposal of the research and industrial communities, and the citizenship (the EOSC and other open-access repositories will be used), whilst considering the Intellectual Property Right; research will be published under Golden Open Access terms. ANIPH includes the priority use of Open Research Europe as general open access platform while, some open access platforms/journals with a relevant impact factor will be considered. Moreover, mutual learning mechanisms and approaches (public engagement, open access, gender balanced actions, project alignment with societal needs, transparency) according to Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) will be deployed. Several actions will be held, to: a) disseminate research results; b) inform society in an accessible and inclusive way about the current research; and c) raise awareness about bioeconomy topics.

Other Open Science practices: Reproducibility of results will be assured by several means: the DMP, FAIR, preprints, open peer-review; Open access to the project physical results, e.g., product samples and the open-source software AI tools and biomaterials datasets; All relevant knowledge actors, including citizens and consumers will be involved across the R&I through public engagement strategy and tailored actions such as workshops, focus groups, etc., and create an enabling framework conditions (e.g. open tools and policy recommendations delivered). Besides, ANIPH will share information and results with the Knowledge Centre for Bioeconomy (KCB), JRC, Proecesses4Planet, Circular Bio-based Europe JU, also clustering activities with other EU projects.

8.2.1. Measures to be implemented

Open Science (OS) is, more than a requirement, an Ethical obligation to respond to complex and interconnected environmental, social, and economic challenges by providing solutions to advance environmental sustainability and respect for the planet's biological and cultural diversity, foster sustainable social and economic development and promote democracy and peace[4]. Open Science includes:

- **Transparent documentation, methodologies and peer review:** Accessible research methods and outputs widely available for rigorous review and transparent evaluation processes improve the quality, reproducibility and impact of science.
- **Use of open sources and open access to the research:** use of open access platforms, repositories for publications, open source code for software, open labs and virtual research environments, and digital research services, in particular those that allow identifying unambiguously scientific objects by persistent unique identifiers (DOI), ensure that data are available following the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) principles, supported by regular curation and maintenance.
- **Facilitate access to underlying information and empirical data** encompasses the use of open data infrastructures that enable collaborative and multidisciplinary data analysis,

required to support the requirements of different communities. Restrictions should be justified due to the protection of human rights, confidentiality and right to privacy, legal processes, or intellectual property rights, among others.

- **Communicate the research to the society at large:** Opening-up practices and public tools make the scientific process more inclusive and accessible to the broader society, including the adoption of new forms of collaboration such as citizen science and community involvement in co-creation methodologies. This results in an enhanced dialogue with stakeholders (policymakers, civil society, industry, and public administrations) that ensures the uptake of results as they respond to societal needs and concerns. Moreover, open dialogue with society promotes the inclusion of diversity in science and fosters opportunities for scientific education and capacity development.

To sum up, OS aims at “Transparency, accessibility, and solving societal challenges”. In addition, “Open science principles require that such communication with various societal stakeholders should not only be a one-way communication (academics inform the public about their research results) but instead should be a two-way communication, in which relevant stakeholders should have a significant impact on the formulation of research questions”[5].

ANIPH will be based on more collaborative, interdisciplinary, open, transparent, and reproducible science. **Adopting Open Science (OS) principles, ANIPH will support the use of plastic alternatives to reduce the negative impact of the agri-food industry.** This requires an approach that considers consciously adopting an ‘open’ approach to science (by, for example, exploring unforeseen turns in results). ANIPH results will be deposited into the project website and public repositories (EOSC[6] /Open Aire[7]) as a research data repository and they will be accessible for third parties to exploit, reproduce and disseminate, free of charge. Both self-archiving (“green” open access) and open-access publishing (“gold” open access) will be considered.

8.3. RRI (Responsible Research Innovation)

Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) is critical within the Ethical dimension of the project[8]. Specifically, in regards: (a) **Ethical research**, including its lawful appropriateness and the issues concerning data privacy, as well as the considerations specifically concerning the involvement of deprived, marginalised or vulnerable collectives; (b) **Research integrity**, respecting academic freedom and human rights and supporting high-quality and transparent research; and (c) **Social acceptability and alignment**.

In sum, RRI should consider, as stated verbatim by RRI Tools¹ (Figure 2):

1. **Diversity and inclusion:** Be sensitive to research biases, include diverse voices and make results beneficial to a wider community
2. **Anticipation and Reflection:** Think about the purposes and possible implications of your research and its outcomes and envisage all possible strategies and methods
3. **Openness and Transparency:** Share objectives, methods and, whenever possible and appropriate, results, and inform about potential conflicts of interests
4. **Responsiveness and Adaptive Change:** Be responsive to changes and external inputs, adapting your research plans to changing social values and expectations

¹ <https://rri-tools.eu/>

Diversity and inclusion	Anticipation and reflection	Open and transparent	Responsive and adaptative
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Sensitive and aware of research biases •Diverse voices •Wider-community perspective 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Possible applications and outcomes •Risk-benefit analysis 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Objectives and methods •Open results •Communication 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Responsible to changes and external input •Changing social values or changing communities may change the research plan

Figure 1 Principles of RRI (source: RRI tools)

RRI should consider during the whole lifecycle and evaluate the following dimensions:

Ethics Research integrity and ethical acceptability of the R&I outcomes	Gender equality Human resources, decision bodies and research dimension	Governance Structural changes to include all these issues in the R&I system	Open access To results from publicly funded research, privacy issues and even open science	Public engagement Towards a more open and inclusive R&I	Science education Provide competences for the responsible citizens society needs

Figure 2 RRI dimensions (source: RRI tools)

Research integrity:

ANIPH will uphold the highest standards of rigour according to ethical, legal, and professional frameworks and will provide a culture of integrity, transparency, and accountable research, reviewing the project's progress regularly and openly.

Research Integrity (RI) is one of the most important Ethical issues in research (and, in developing and innovating new products and services, specifically if these are publicly funded). RI is defined by “Rigour, Honesty, respect for life, Law and Public Good and Responsible communications (Listening and informing)”[9]. In other words, RI implies **Honesty, rigour, transparency, care, and respect for all participants and accountability**². **Informed consent from the ethical point of view:**

Why informed consent?[10]

- [Protection](#)
- [Autonomy](#)
- [Preventing abusive conduct](#)
- [Trust](#)
- [Self-ownership](#)
- [Non-domination](#)
- [Personal integrity](#)

Explicit informed consent by data subjects is a vital part of any process involving human subjects (age, gender, education level, and socioeconomic background of affected individuals, working conditions, health and safety at the workplace, fair treatment, freedom of association, training skills...), to respect their rights of free choice and data privacy. The whole consortium will ensure that the potential subjects can reach a truly informed

² Research Integrity means conducting research in such a way that allows others to have confidence and trust in the methods and the findings of the research. It relates both to the scientific integrity of conducted research and to the professional integrity of researchers. <https://www.ed.ac.uk/research-office/research-integrity/what-is-research-integrity>

decision about whether or not to participate in the research. Their explicit informed consent must be given freely, without coercion, and must be based on a clear understanding of what participation involves, including any personal data to be processed and the purposes of the same. Each partner responsible for involving end-users will guarantee the collection of explicit consents, signed by representatives as stated above before any empirical activity affecting them, including but not limited to collecting personal data.

As in the case of data protection, *consolidated hands-on guidance* will be collected from relevant sources at an early stage of the project.

A preliminary investigation has revealed some principles that should be considered for achieving informed consent from users participating in the project, concretely in tasks related with WP5-6-11-12:

- Each potential subject must be adequately informed of the aims, methods, anticipated benefits and potential hazards of the research and any discomfort it may entail;
- The expected participation of individuals and the approximate duration of each activity;
- Any documentation given to potential participants should be comprehensible, and there should be an opportunity for them to raise any issues of concern;
- Consent should be given in writing and records of consent should be maintained; considering the particularities in the workplace and the risks that it may entail
- Potential participants must be informed that they are free to withdraw consent to participation at any time;
- There should be a procedure for making complaints and participants should be made aware of this;
- All participants must be volunteers. Considerable care should be taken where consent is sought from those in a dependent position;
- Any inducement offered to participants should be declared and should be by appropriate guidelines.

Specific considerations concerning working conditions and operators' involvement:

- Workers representatives' consent: If workers are involved during their regular schedule, and if obtaining individual consent from each worker is not feasible, labour union representatives will discuss and agree on the participation with the staff and then, sign the consent.
- Consent Form: The information in the consent form should be individualized and communicated in a way that is more sensitive to the needs of participants. The number of questions in the "Consent Form" has to be appropriate to each participant's profile (high-skilled workers and managers, chiefs and directors, low-skilled workers, labour union officers, etc.);

As previously introduced, ANIPH will collect and process various personal data, mainly offline but potentially online as well. Additionally, the project will potentially process sensitive personal data (e.g., ideology, incidentally collected during co-creation workshops, values/ beliefs, and even health conditions collected in task 5.3). Any unnecessary data unexpectedly received will be then discharged. Therefore, some of the ANIPH activities envisaging the involvement of human participants (Task 5.3) will require their informed consent to be carried out.

The **informed consent** of participants will allow beneficiaries to 1) process personal data; 2) obtain and use images and/or recordings of participants for project purposes only; and/or 3) observe workers in the workplace.

Informed consent to the processing of personal data will be required for any activity involving some of the forms of processing of personal data identified in Article 4 (2) GDPR: collection, recording,

organisation, structuring, storage, adaptation or alteration, retrieval, consultation, use, disclosure by transmission, dissemination or otherwise making available, alignment or combination, restriction, erasure, or destruction. In addition, informed consent will be required for video/audio recording or image taking for those activities for whose primary purpose it is essential, as well as for the dissemination tasks of the project.

Whilst not restricted to them, these tasks involve participants, and are matter of particular concern from an Ethical perspective:

- T2.4 Selection of safe raw materials and additives, and preliminary adaptations
- T2.5 Development of ANIPH AI predictive system and traceability tool
- T5.1 Feed and implementation of the tools of the ICT platform
- T5.2 Safety assessment
- T6.3 Public engagement because it involves direct interaction with citizens and the collection of perception data
- T8.1 Cellulose@probiotic additives development as an alternative to antibiotics
- T8.2 PHBV and PHN-based adhesives and coatings manufacturing
- T8.3 Manufacturing of wound dressing and packaging at small scale with programmed biodegradation
- T10.4 Validation in a real environment by *in vitro* testing of the final ANIPH products
- T11.2 Safety assessment
- T11.3 Sustainability assessment

Issues on data gathering and data protection, as well as responsible AI development are also being addressed.

All volunteer research participants in ANIPH will receive informed consent forms containing basic project information in accessible languages prior to research commencement. Researchers will review the form with participants, providing verbal summaries if needed, before obtaining voluntary consent without pressure. Participants may ask questions and receive clear answers, and must sign and date the consent form, with both parties retaining copies. The completed consent forms will be stored by the relevant Data Controller, ensuring participants understand and consent to data collection and processing within ANIPH.

Ethics and public participation:

Additionally, some ethical issues are intrinsically attached to research in this project . Ethics is an integral part of research that will be considered from the beginning to the end of the project implementation. Thus, all the activities developed along the project will comply with ethical principles and relevant national, EU and international legislation, for example, the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the EU and the European Convention on Human Rights. Provisions of Directive 95/46/EC and the General Data Protection Regulation principles of rights and consent and data processing as stipulated in Articles 6, 7, 10, 12, 25 and 35 (GDPR, 2018g) are shown to be highly relevant to the protection of research participants and service users.

Moreover, Regulatory compliance is within the scope and this project aligns with:

- The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).
- The Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data

and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation).

- Directive 2002/58/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 12 July 2002 concerning the processing of personal data and the protection of privacy in the electronic communications sector - the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the EU (2000/c 364/01).
- Gender policy of the EU and Public Engagement and Responsible Research and Innovation inclusive approach.

Public Participation and stakeholders' involvement

Significant stakeholder engagement, defined as long-term involvement, commitment, and participation (i.e., active contributions to the dialogue), is needed to develop adaptation-integrated strategies that fully reflect the complexities and conflicts that must be explored and negotiated by all stakeholders. ANIPH will encourage the involvement of stakeholders in different ways but must be always aligned with **the IAP2 Core Values for Public Participation** [11], entailing different levels of public participation based on the *Spectrum of Public Participation* (Figure 3), according to the goals of the specific action, its complexity and sensitivity.

Figure 3 IAP2 Spectrum of Public Participation

ANIPH also proposes to engage stakeholders and experts in the definition of the Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD) framework, as well as in the Social Sustainability Assessment that will take place in WP5 and WP11. By having citizens, stakeholders and experts participate in the project, ANIPH will increase its impact and will help raise awareness about the issues and humanitarian challenges tackled by our project.

Three dimensions will be considered:

- **Community readiness** analyses the degree to which a community is ready to take action on an issue, in a specific, dimensional, and stratified way. Community efforts, knowledge of the efforts, leadership, willingness or awareness, knowledge and resources should be analysed prior to implementing public engagement methods.
- **Community engagement** and **Community participation** in citizen science activities, workshops, and contests will promote the ownership of the project results.
- **Evaluation** of engagement and participatory processes will consider both quantitative factors (e.g. the number of stakeholders; gender balance; equitable representation of age

groups and the diversity of social groups) and qualitative factors (e.g. the direct and indirect impact the stakeholders had on the processes, activities and decisions taken).

These continuous processes of engagement involve two different ethical issues:

- Human health and bioethics
- Operational ethical issues concerning data protection and informed consent.

Ethical issues arise when co-producing (citizen science) research and innovation with communities or under a multistakeholder perspective.

8.3.1. RRI and Gender

Gender issues are briefly addressed within this section. The RRI principles are relevant for ethics and gender issues promoting gender equality by addressing the representation (or lack thereof) of women in research with the objective to reduce gender segregation. They primarily address:

- The **horizontal and vertical participation of women** in research to promote women in all fields where they are under-represented as well as to increase female participation in management and decision-making positions.
- **Structural change in research institutions** aimed at eliminating structural barriers for women to increase their participation in scientific careers.
- **Integration of gender in the context of research and innovation** to ensure that women's needs and interests are adequately addressed. Explicit gender issues are rarely included in the content, and it is argued that research results are not valid or reliable if they only consider male research subjects.

Gender has a relevant role in decisions related to health, social care or sustainable consumption[12], [13] and it should be considered in the design of novel sustainable products. Thus, ANIPH will integrate the gender analysis during the whole project lifecycle, including the sampling, recruitment, data analysis and evaluation, integrating women's skills, knowledge and capacities and supporting the deployment of the tasks planned.

Concerning RRI and gender³, ANIPH will integrate the gender equality dimension within the project tasks. Apart from embedding gender from the research proposal to the end of the project, gender

Increasing women's participation is a required changeover for fostering environmental sustainability and productivity gains, creating mutual benefits and greater returns across the SDGs, including SDG 5 (Gender equality and women's empowerment), SDG 12 (Responsible consumption and production) and SDG 11 (Sustainable cities and communities).

balance will be promoted in decision-making, in the formed R&I teams and reflected in the elaboration of deliverables, papers and scientific and technical outcomes. If required, capacity building, non-formal training and protocols will be delivered to the whole consortium.

8.3.2. Environmental Ethics

Environmental ethics is the discipline in philosophy that studies the moral relationship of human beings to, and the value and moral status of, the environment and its non-human contents.

Applied to ANIPH, it is a matter of direct application, considering:

³ <https://rri-tools.eu/gender-equality>

1. The challenge of environmental ethics to the anthropocentrism (i.e., human-centredness) embedded in traditional Moral Philosophy & Ethical thinking
2. The connection of deep ecology, feminist environmental ethics, and social ecology to politics
3. The attempt to apply traditional ethical theories, including consequentialism, deontology, and virtue ethics, to support contemporary environmental concerns, plus also the broader concerns of some thinkers with the built environment and the politics of poverty
4. The ethics of sustainability and climate change

Connections between environmental destruction, unequal resource consumption, poverty and the global economic order have been discussed extensively in the literature. It is worth remarking the works by Mark Sagoff (1988)[14], arguing that "as citizens rather than consumers" people are concerned about values, which cannot plausibly be reduced to mere ordered preferences or quantified in monetary terms. Sagoff's distinction between people as consumers and people as citizens was intended to blunt the use of cost-benefit analysis as the final arbiter in discussions about nature's value. Thus, cost-benefit analysis cannot be a basis for an ethic of sustainability any more than for an ethic of biodiversity. Likewise, the development of ecological economics has been included within the Ethics discussion, as a common ground between economists and environmental policy-makers.

8.3.2.1. *Environmental Regulations in ANIPH*

Concerning environmental risks, the ANIPH project observes these regulations:

- Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) 2020/2174 on shipments of waste
- Equipment legislative requirements – e.g., Machinery Directive 2006/42/EC
- Safety and quality control of the processing – whenever relevant, e.g., ISO 9000 standards, etc.

EU-27: Biocompatibility and Safety Requirements:

- Essential Requirements of the EU Medical Device Regulation (2017/745)
- The harmonised standard EN ISO 10993-1:2009 provides a "presumption of conformity" for demonstrating biological safety
- Manufacturers are expected to perform a biological risk assessment and all relevant tests (per ISO 10993 series) for any device in contact with human tissue
- ANIPH partners in charge, in case of successful exploitation after the project, should monitor and report device performance and adverse events

Although environmental risks are comprehensively addressed elsewhere in the project documentation, these will be revised – as a whole – for traceability and integration within the overall SSbD Project evaluation.

8.4. Ethics and Artificial Intelligence (AI)

This section outlines the ethical considerations around the development of an AI predictive tool for PHA-based material properties, biodegradation, and ecotoxicity as part of the ANIPH project. The development and deployment of AI systems, particularly those used in scientific and industrial applications, must comply with the OECD AI Principles and the EU AI Act to ensure responsible innovation [15], [16].

8.4.1. AI transparency and explainability

One of the core principles that lays out a Human Rights-centred Approach to the Ethics of AI is Transparency and Explainability (T&E). The level of transparency and explainability should be appropriate to the context, without any tension between any other principles. That being said, the ANIPH AI prediction tool will be developed with a strong emphasis on T&E, encouraging trust and accountability. That means

- a) Comprehensive technical documentation will be maintained, detailing the model architecture, training data sources, and decision-making logic.
- b) Stakeholders interacting with the AI system will be informed about its capabilities, limitations, and the nature of its outputs.
- c) Where feasible, the tool will include mechanisms to provide interpretable outputs, enabling users to understand and validate predictions.

8.4.2. AI fairness and bias mitigation

Even though the AI tool is not intended for use in socially sensitive domains, fairness remains a priority. According to the tenth principle, *AI actors should promote social justice, fairness and non-discrimination while taking an inclusive approach to ensure AI' benefits are accessible to all* (Unesco's Ethics of Artificial Intelligence, 2021). Training and validation datasets will be evaluated for representativeness and potential biases, especially if human-generated data or proxies are used. Moreover, data collection and preprocessing will follow rigorous standards to ensure quality, relevance, and fairness. Lastly, if biases are detected, corrective measures such as data augmentation or algorithmic adjustments will be implemented.

8.4.3. AI robustness and safety

In order to ensure the technical robustness and safety of the AI system, a systematic risk assessment will be conducted throughout the AI lifecycle to identify potential failure modes and mitigation strategies. The tool will undergo extensive testing, including edge cases and stress scenarios to ensure reliability and resiliency. Moreover, fall back procedures will be implemented to handle unexpected behavior or degraded performance.

8.4.4. Human oversight and intervention

Critical decisions based on AI outputs will require human validation particularly in research or industrial contexts. Furthermore, to ensure traceability, all stages of the AI lifecycle, including data handling, model training and inference, will be traceable to support accountability and auditability. Responsibilities for oversight will be clearly defined among ANIPH partners, ensuring appropriate intervention capabilities.

8.4.5. Compliance with EU AI Act requirements

Given that the ANIPH's AI predictive system is going to be used to understand which descriptors or structural features of targeted materials influence their processability, toxicity and biodegradation properties, respectively, it qualifies as high risk AI system under the EU AI Act (Regulation (EU) 2024/1689). As such, the tool will ensure full compliance with the applicable legal and technical obligations. The tool will undergo the required conformity assessment procedures including technical documentation and risk evaluation. Moreover, mechanisms will be established to monitor system performance and address any emerging risks or incidents.

8.5. Ethics and human tissues

This section addresses the ethical considerations surrounding the use of human tissues in the ANIPH project, particularly in relation to PHA-based materials for wound healing applications. Ethical management of human tissues requires adherence to strict protocols that respect donor rights, ensure proper consent, and maintain compliance with international bioethical standards.

8.5.1. Tissue acquisition ethics

The literature was revised, covering ethical concerns regarding:

1. **PHA in contact with human tissues** (biocompatibility, toxicity, regulatory compliance)
2. **Issues derived from the innovation regarding the use of antibiotics and its alternatives in humanitarian contexts** (infection risks, equity, humanitarian ethics)
3. **Environmental challenges concerning the reverse logistics** (waste management, green supply chains, cross-contamination risks)
4. **Human health effects** (exposure to additives, long-term risks)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are emerging biopolymers proposed for use in medical applications such as wound dressings. This preliminary revision examines the ethical and safety concerns in four key areas: (1) **PHA in contact with human tissue**, (2) **absence of antibiotics in wound dressings for conflict zones**, (3) **environmental sustainability and reverse logistics**, and (4) **general human health effects from PHA materials and additives**. 1. PHA in Contact with Human Tissue

8.5.1.1. PHA in Contact with Human Tissue

PHAs (such as PHB, PHBV, etc.) exhibit good *in vitro* and *in vivo* biocompatibility according to previous studies confirming low cytotoxicity and minimal inflammatory response. Since altering the crystallinity of the polymer may change the degradation rate and mechanical properties of the material, further tests will be carried out to confirm whether they retain their mechanical and biological properties, thus confirming that the interaction of the wound with the material over time is not affected.

Biocompatibility and Toxicity:

The synergism between the high biocompatibility of these microbial materials, the extraordinary adjustability of their stiffness, strength, elasticity, crystallinity, degradability, etc., in statu nascendi by adapting the bioprocess (strain and feedstock selection), and the emerging knowledge of novel techniques to process PHA into custom-made devices makes it very likely that these multi-faceted biopolyesters can become widely accepted and implemented workhorses to treat diverse diseases and injuries in a not too distant future. However, a lot of R&D work still needs to be dedicated to design and evaluate to optimum PHA-based formulation for defined applications in this steadily emerging field[17].

PHAs (such as PHB, PHBV, etc.) are generally reported to be biocompatible and non-toxic in biomedical contexts. Extensive in vitro and in vivo studies indicate that PHA polymers do not elicit significant cytotoxic or carcinogenic effects. Moreover, the monomeric by-products of PHA degradation (e.g. 3-hydroxybutyrate) occur naturally in human blood and are metabolised safely. In comparison to many traditional plastics, PHAs have “null toxicity” and support cell attachment and growth[18]. A good cytocompatibility and no evidence of carcinogenesis seems to be present in animal implantation studies of PHAs to date.

However, biocompatibility is contingent on material purity: for instance, impurities – such as bacterial endotoxins (lipopolysaccharides from the PHA production process) - can provoke inflammation if not removed: it is required to ensure medical-grade PHA is thoroughly purified (e.g. through solvent extraction, washing, and reprecipitation) .

Altered Crystallinity and Tissue Response:

One factor influencing PHA performance in tissue contact is polymer crystallinity. PHAs can range from highly crystalline (e.g. homopolymer PHB) to more amorphous co-polymers, and this property affects degradation rate and mechanical behaviour. High crystallinity PHAs tend to degrade slowly in biological environments – an “unchanged local pH value” during degradation is a benefit for biocompatibility. Still, excessive **crystallinity can hinder bio resorption**, and it could pose long-term irritation or infection risks if a device remains intact longer than intended. To address this, researchers suggest using less crystalline PHA co-polymers or blends to accelerate degradation in vivo¹⁷. According to this same research, to blend PHB with more amorphous polymers or additives can disrupt crystallinity and a lower crystallinity PHAs tend to be more elastomeric and degrade more readily, which can be **favourable for tissue integration** and regeneration.

Ethically, designers of PHA-based implants or dressings must balance safety/stability vs. biodegradability. Overly crystalline PHAs risk long-term persistence (a potential hazard), whereas overly rapid degradation might compromise support to healing tissue. However, it must be noted that **there is no indication** that crystallinity itself introduces new chemical toxicity.

PHAs have shown great promise as biocompatible, bioresorbable materials for human tissue contact, but responsible innovation demands rigorous pre-clinical validation and regulatory compliance. **Validation also involves degradation assessments** – both in vitro (e.g. in simulated body fluids) and in vivo – to measure degradation by-products and ensure they are safe. To adhere to international QA frameworks – e.g., international standards (ISO 10993 series) - not only fulfils legal obligations but upholds the ethical principle of patient safety, ensuring a consistent, science-based approach to toxicity testing.

8.5.1.2. Absence of Antibiotics in Wound Dressings for Conflict Zones

The proposal to use PHA wound dressings without antibiotics in conflict zones raises ethical questions regarding infection control and the standard of care provided in humanitarian settings. War wounds are highly prone to infection, contaminated with a diverse range of foreign bodies,

bacteria, and contaminants, leading to a high incidence of infection[19]. Inadequate initial treatment (due to chaotic environments, scarcity of resources and mass casualties) significantly elevates this risk [20]. Inappropriate management may lead to severe complications, e.g., chronic osteomyelitis, sepsis, amputations, or death.

Addressing antibiotic use, nosocomial transmission and infectious sequelae are a current clinical management and research priority.

Data from recent conflicts show alarmingly high rates of **multi-drug resistant (MDR) bacterial infections** in war injuries.

Common pathogens include *Acinetobacter baumannii* (“Iraqibacter”), MRSA, and other hospital-acquired strains, which complicate treatment because first-line antibiotics are often ineffective[21]. The presence or absence of an antimicrobial agent in a dressing can influence local bacterial load. A *systematic concern* is that **the wound may be more likely to become overtly infected without topical antibiotics**, especially if systemic antibiotics are unavailable or insufficient. Infection in turn is a major driver of mortality in trauma – even with prompt care, an infected wound can lead to sepsis and death, particularly in resource-scarce settings[22]. WHO guidance notes that antibiotics alone do not reach the source of the wound infection, that they are necessary but not sufficient (World Health Organisation, n.d.). **Given this, the ethical question is: are we compromising patient outcomes?**

Some evidence suggests that modern antimicrobial dressings (which may contain antibiotics or antiseptics like silver) help reduce bioburden and prevent infection progression[23]. Unfortunately, quantitative data comparing “antibiotic dressing vs. no antibiotic” in conflict conditions are scarce due to ethical and practical barriers to conducting trials in war). Indirect evidence can be drawn from military medicine and general guidelines [23].

The morbidity from wound infections includes prolonged hospitalisation, additional surgeries (e.g. amputations or additional debridement), and long-term disability. Mortality due to sepsis complications may be common. In modern war surgery and conflict-zone field hospitals often operate under austere conditions, where a delayed presentation of the patient is also common ²⁰, ²² thus, if PHA dressings without antibiotics are used, they must be part of a protocol that still includes systemic antibiotic prophylaxis (when available) and meticulous wound care. A core ethical issue is whether providing dressings with no antibiotics in humanitarian settings might constitute a sub-standard therapy or comparable to main therapeutic tools when vulnerable populations are approached and treated. There is a tension between *equity*, *justice* and *practicality*: in war, sometimes the “standard” of a Western hospital simply cannot be achieved, and, ethically, we must ensure we are not needlessly compromising care. One justification for avoiding antibiotics in dressings is the fight against antimicrobial resistance (AMR).

One critical example of the concerns of conflict medicine is multidrug-resistant (MDR) bacteria, which now accounts for the majority of war wound infections across the Middle East region- Reports from civilian, humanitarian and military institutions have identified MDR bacteria as the predominant pathogens causing infections in war wounds in the region. Yet, most facilities in the region do not even have the laboratory capacity to diagnose MDR, leading to significant delays and clinical mismanagement of festering wounds. In addition to the real public health threat that MDR poses to compromised hospital settings in the region, it imposes a gross financial burden on patients and their families ²¹.

Humanitarian organisations like MSF have raised alarm that conflict zones are hotbeds of AMR, with war wounds commonly infected by MDR organisms. Thus, also the **indiscriminate use of antibiotics (especially prolonged broad-spectrum courses or adding antibiotics to dressings without clear**

indication) could worsen resistance. The ICRC has developed antibiotic stewardship protocols for war wounds, aiming to “*enhance antibiotic stewardship, reduce misuse of antibiotics*” in conflicts. *In conflict scenarios, comprehensive microbiology services are rarely available, whereas wound infections are very common. The ICRC Antibiotic Protocol for Weapon Wounded is an evidence informed protocol created to enhance antibiotic stewardship, reduce misuse of antibiotics and provides recommendations for both prophylaxis and treatment of established infection*[24].

Traditional “antibiotic dressings” often contain agents like cetrimide²⁰, neomycin, gentamicin, or mupirocin incorporated into a gauze or collagen matrix. From a public health ethics perspective, there is a duty to preserve antibiotic efficacy for the future. This means using antibiotics judiciously even in acute situations. Consequently, **removing antibiotics from dressings could be an intentional strategy to prevent overuse**, relying instead on good surgical care and systemic antibiotics only when necessary.

From an ethical standpoint, if a PHA dressing without antibiotics is to be used, it should be compared against available alternatives. The current ethical consensus is that in conflict care, **the highest priority is life and limb saving through surgical intervention**, with local dressings being secondary support. If PHA dressings do not impede the standard practices (and indeed if they encourage proper wound care by simplifying logistics), their use can be justified. **Transparent communication with humanitarian patients is also key: they should know if a new type of dressing is being used and why (particularly if it deviates from what they might consider “normal” care).** **This respects patient autonomy and builds trust, even in crises.**

8.5.1.3. Environmental Sustainability and Reverse Logistics

Figure 4 Environmental sustainability and reverse logistics

A notable benefit of PHA-based wound dressings is their environmental sustainability, especially in settings where medical waste disposal is challenging. This section explores the life-cycle impacts of PHAs, the feasibility of “green” supply chains and reverse logistics, and potential risks like cross-contamination with conventional plastics. The ethical lens here is twofold: environmental stewardship (responsibility to “do no harm” to the environment and communities) and practical logistics in humanitarian operations.

Waste management and Life Cycle Analysis (LCA) of PHAs: Conventional plastic medical waste (e.g. used bandages with synthetic polymer backings) contributes significantly to pollution, often ending up in incinerators or landfills. In contrast, PHAs are **biodegradable** biopolymers – they can be broken

down by microbes into natural substances like water, carbon dioxide (and biomass) under the right conditions, offering a compelling advantage in a life-cycle perspective. A PHA wound dressing made from renewable resources could have a lower environmental footprint than a petrochemical-based dressing. Life cycle assessment studies indicate that PHAs can outperform not only conventional plastics (like polypropylene) but even other bioplastics (like PLA) in certain impact categories. Key environmental advantages include the renewable feedstock, that PHA products can biodegrade in natural environments (soil or marine) within months to a few years. This means a discarded PHA dressing is far less likely to become long-lasting litter or harmful microplastic fragments.

In humanitarian contexts, these benefits are magnified. Conflict and disaster zones often lack formal waste management – no systematic recycling or safe trash disposal. By using biodegradable PHA dressings and **packaging**, the ANIPH project aims to *avoid pollution in humanitarian contexts where appropriate waste management systems are usually not feasible*.

Moreover, as technology improves and if renewable energy and waste feedstocks are used, PHAs' production impacts are dropping. The literature encourages *integrating PHA production into bio-refineries and waste treatment facilities* to improve sustainability and economics¹⁷. Besides, a comprehensively 'greener' and environmentally responsible supply chain, logistics and transport management involves the consideration of all these factors at each step: sourcing, manufacturing, distribution, use, and reverse logistics (return or disposal). The **logistical feasibility** in conflict zones is a critical angle: Traditional medical supply chains face difficulties in retrieving used products (reverse logistics) because the priority is delivering new aid, not collecting waste. PHA dressings offer a form of **built-in reverse logistics via biodegradability** – even if you cannot physically retrieve the used dressing, the environmental harm is being reduced. Also, traceability and forecasting can help ensure that the PHAs are degrading as intended and not accumulating. From a feasibility perspective, biodegradable dressings reduce the burden on local waste systems. Medical teams won't need to burn or bury as much waste (both of which have downsides: open burning can emit toxic smoke; burying can contaminate water). To manage this, **training and clear labelling** are needed: health workers should know that the PHA dressing and its packaging are compostable/biodegradable and ideally dispose of them separately from recyclables.

In conclusion, **PHA-based wound dressings offer substantial environmental advantages** in challenging settings: their biodegradable nature alleviates the burden of medical waste disposal, aligning with ethical obligations to protect the environment and local populations from pollution.

8.5.1.4. General Human Health Effects of PHA Materials and Additives

While PHAs are largely biocompatible, the **overall safety profile** of PHA-based products depends on more than the polymer itself. Additives used to process or enhance PHAs (plasticisers, stabilisers, reinforcement fibres/nanoparticles, etc.) can introduce health risks. Additionally, chronic exposure scenarios – for instance, consumers using many PHA-based items over time, or communities exposed to environmental residues – need to be considered. This section discusses the potential human health impacts from additives in PHAs, the possible effects of long-term exposure to PHA degradation products or microplastics, and the frameworks for post-market surveillance and risk assessment to manage these concerns.

Figure 5 General human health effects of PHA materials and additives

Pure PHAs like PHB are often stiff and brittle; to make flexible films or dressings, manufacturers may add **plasticisers**. Some phthalates (DEHP, DBP) are classified as reproductive toxicants and possible human carcinogens. Thus, transparency is an ethical matter in regard the manufacturers' practices and the use of certain additives and civil surveillance mechanisms might be required [25]. Similarly, **reinforcement agents** might be added to PHAs to improve mechanical properties. These could be fibres (glass fibre, carbon fibre, cellulose) or nano-fillers (nanoclay, silica, graphene). While these can strengthen the material or alter its degradation, they might introduce inhalation or tissue reaction hazards, especially for workers in manufacturing settings.

The **European Chemicals Agency (ECHA)** and other regulatory bodies keep lists of restricted substances in medical products – ensuring no prohibited or high-risk additive is used as part of ethical manufacturing.

No matter how much pre-market testing is done, unanticipated health effects can sometimes emerge when a product is used in the real world, across diverse populations and over longer durations. **Post-market surveillance (PMS)** is therefore a cornerstone of medical device safety. Regulatory authorities require manufacturers to actively monitor and report any adverse events or trends once the product is on the market [26]. For PHA wound dressings, potential signals to watch might include incidence of wound irritation or allergic reactions beyond expected, or any other unusual infection patterns (perhaps related to material handling), or any systemic reactions. An ethical company will have a robust PMS plan: collecting feedback from fieldwork during the project in using the dressings and setting up a system to capture any adverse incident. One emerging area of surveillance is **environmental health monitoring** tackled within the SSbD framework.

8.5.2. Donor rights and dignity

The ethical foundation for isolating human skin cells begins with donor autonomy, informed consent, and dignity. Consent must be fully informed, voluntary, and specific, as per the principles outlined in the Declaration of Helsinki (WMA) and EU Directive 2004/23/EC on human tissue use. Consent forms must clearly explain the purpose, risks, potential commercial uses, storage periods, and the right to withdraw consent at any time without repercussions.

Transparency in the collection process is critical. Donors must be informed if the cells will be used for commercial applications, shared internationally, or stored long-term. To uphold dignity,

anonymisation protocols—such as pseudonymisation and irreversible coding—must be implemented to protect privacy under GDPR (EU Regulation 2016/679).

Donor engagement through feedback mechanisms (e.g., opt-in for research updates or results) fosters trust. Furthermore, cultural sensitivities—especially in humanitarian contexts where ANIPH products may be deployed—must be respected. Tailored consent procedures should reflect local customs and languages, with special attention to vulnerable populations. Provisions must address power imbalances and avoid coercion, particularly in low-resource or emergency settings.

8.5.3. Storage and disposal protocols

Ethical tissue storage hinges on security, traceability, and respectful handling. Human skin cells must be stored in validated, access-controlled environments with proper temperature monitoring, following ISO 20387:2018 standards for biobanking. Data on the sample's origin, storage conditions, and chain-of-custody must be meticulously documented to comply with Good Laboratory Practice (GLP) and OECD guidelines.

For disposal, tissues should be discarded respectfully when research is concluded or consent is withdrawn, using biosecure incineration or other approved biomedical disposal methods. Researchers must develop policies governing how long unused samples are retained, who can authorize their destruction, and how this is recorded.

When transferring samples between institutions or countries, Material Transfer Agreements (MTAs) must specify permissible uses, access restrictions, and conditions for return or destruction. This is particularly important for tissues with potential downstream use in commercial or diagnostic tools, or those deployed in humanitarian scenarios where oversight may vary.

8.5.4. Compliance with bioethics regulations

Human skin cell research must conform to a network of EU, national, and international bioethics frameworks. Key regulations include:

- **EU Directive 2004/23/EC** and its technical directives (2006/17/EC and 2006/86/EC), which govern tissue procurement, testing, processing, preservation, storage, and distribution.
- **General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)** ensuring data privacy and control for donors.
- **WHO Guidance on Ethics in Health Research**, emphasizing equity, benefit-sharing, and protection of vulnerable groups.
- **National-level biomedical ethics laws**, often requiring dual approval from scientific and ethics committees.

Ethical review by an **Independent Ethics Committee (IEC)** or **Institutional Review Board (IRB)** is mandatory **before** tissue collection begins. These bodies must ensure that the study design upholds respect for persons, beneficence, and justice. Documentation of approval must include:

- Consent protocols
- Anonymisation strategies
- Risk-benefit analysis
- Cultural context considerations (especially for deployments in humanitarian crises)

Post-approval, **compliance monitoring** is essential. This includes periodic audits, annual ethics reporting, and channels for whistleblowing or reporting ethical breaches—particularly important when working in low-governance environments.

For projects involving **humanitarian deployments**, there must be additional safeguards:

- Local ethics committee approvals (where feasible)
- Ethical impact assessments on local communities
- Transparency in data use and equitable benefit-sharing

8.6. Ethics and Public Participation

Ethical considerations in ANIPH ensure that scientific activities are conducted with integrity, fairness, and respect for fundamental human rights. Researchers are expected to consider the broader societal implications of their work, promoting accountability and fostering public trust. Moreover, actively involving citizens, civil society, and stakeholders throughout the research process and public engagement activities enriches the knowledge produced, ensuring that it reflects diverse perspectives and societal needs.

The strict alignment to GDPR will guarantee that data are handled responsibly. For example, information of newsletter subscribers and registrees to project events will be collected, handled and stored according to the GDPR regulations. A Privacy Notice is available on the project website (<https://aniph.eu/privacy-notice/>) to provide subscribers with very detailed information on data being collected and the purposes of such collection. Users have the option to opt in/opt out and thus to decide whether they want to receive project-related updates and communications, being thus the data used for the declared purposes only. Should users opt out, their information will be destroyed once the purpose of their subscription (i.e. newsletter or event) is no longer applicable.

8.7. Ethical risk assessment and mitigation

During the Project lifecycle, and apart from the ethics reporting (mid-term and final reports), ethical risks will be surveyed by revising the technical work after its submission as long as reviewers of each Deliverable will have at their disposal the present Ethics guidelines.

Specifically, risks will be revised regarding these activities:

Table 1 Timeline of main ethics revisions

Month (M)	Task (T)	Plain description
M13	T2.5 (WP2) – M12	AI system design
M24	D1.3 Mid term ethics report	
M27	D8.1 and D8.2 (M26)	Biodegradable wound dressing and packaging
M37	D8.3, D8.4 and D8.5 (M36)	Small-scale of wound dressings and AI predictive model assessment
M47	D10.4	Validation in a real environment by in vitro testing of the final ANIPH products
M47	T7.3	Final Ethics report and analysis

This ethical framework provides a robust foundation for ensuring that the ANIPH project's technological innovations are deployed in a manner that maximises benefit while systematically addressing potential ethical challenges in humanitarian applications.

The literature supports ANIPH's objective to "develop ANIPH Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD) framework" (SO8), while suggesting several ethical considerations:

1. Multi-stakeholder engagement: The framework should incorporate perspectives from humanitarian workers, healthcare practitioners in conflict settings, and potential patients to ensure the design meets actual needs rather than presumed ones.
2. Lifecycle assessment comprehensiveness: The economic and social sustainability metrics (KPI11) must include genuine evaluation of accessibility in humanitarian contexts, considering the target price (25€/kg) in relation to humanitarian budget constraints.
3. Information transparency: The contribution to "Information and Labelling Systems" (KPI12) should include clear communication about the limitations and intended use cases of these materials, avoiding overpromising or minimizing potential drawbacks.

In essence, the introduction of PHA wound dressings should be guided by a commitment to *do no harm* – to patients, to communities, and to the environment. With proper validation and oversight, PHA dressings could represent an innovation that aligns medical care with sustainable and ethical best practices, addressing immediate needs while safeguarding future well-being.

Table 2 Ethical concerns and recommended mitigation strategies

Ethical Dimension	Concerns	Mitigation
Safety & Health (PHA in Human Tissue)	Risks of endotoxin contamination	Rigorous ISO 10993 testing
	Unknown effects of altered crystallinity	Proper sterilisation/purification
Equity (Absence of Antibiotics in Conflict Dressings)	Potentially higher infection rates in war injuries	Transparency about care levels Ethical antibiotic stewardship
Environmental Sustainability (Reverse Logistics)	Risk of greenwashing if waste management is poor	Clear labelling & waste segregation
	Complex end-of-life disposal	SSbD analysis
Additive Exposure & Long-Term Health	Chronic low-level toxicity not well-studied	Perform extended toxicological assessments
	Need post-market surveillance, if commercially exploited	Strong post-market reporting & risk management

8.7.1. Risk identification methodology

Ex ante ethical impact assessment matrix. Specific ethical considerations for humanitarian contexts.

PHA-based wound dressings are expected to be safe for human health, but vigilance is needed. The base polymers have a good biocompatibility track record.

Long-term and chronic exposure risks appear low, especially compared to conventional plastics, since PHAs do not persist and their metabolites are benign.

Nevertheless, comprehensive risk assessments must include worst-case exposure scenarios, and ongoing post-market surveillance should verify the safety assumptions in real-world conditions. By adhering to international safety standards and ethical risk management practices, manufacturers and health providers can ensure that the introduction of PHA wound dressings benefits patients and society without unintended adverse health consequences.

Table 3 Risk-benefit and mitigation (ex-ante; baseline)

Dimension	Description	Mitigation measures
Safety (human health) and research integrity	The efficacy of literature mining depends crucially on the methodological robustness of the systematic review protocol—including comprehensive search string development, inclusion/exclusion criteria specification, and inter-rater reliability assessment mechanisms	<p>The feasibility of constructing a sufficiently robust predictive system from these data sources warrants deeper analytical consideration:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data density thresholds: The proposal lacks specificity regarding the minimum data density requirements across various physicochemical, biological, and toxicological domains necessary for developing statistically valid predictive models. • Dimensional coverage assessment: A systematic gap analysis framework would be essential for evaluating whether the collated datasets achieve sufficient coverage across all relevant PHA formulation parameters to enable comprehensive predictive capabilities. • Temporal validity considerations: The dynamic nature of materials science research necessitates explicit mechanisms for continuous dataset updating and recalibration to maintain predictive validity as the knowledge landscape evolves.
Non-maleficence principle in humanitarian aid context & conflict zones	The implementation of wound dressings in conflict areas requires special safeguards	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Contextualised informed consent: Standard consent procedures may be unfeasible in humanitarian emergency situations. • Post-implementation monitoring: Mechanisms for monitoring adverse effects in vulnerable populations are not specified.
Intervention sustainability	The project's implicit economisation of biodegradation (through mechanisms like target pricing) raises fundamental questions about the distribution of benefits across diverse socioeconomic contexts. The economic accessibility of resulting technologies requires systematic consideration.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technological dependency: how to avoid creating new forms of dependency in already fragile contexts. • Local capacity building: Absence of strategies to develop local capabilities in managing these advanced biomaterials.
Bioethical considerations	The ANIPH proposal sustains and maintains primary bioethical considerations for human tissue interfaces; however, ethical risks arise. For instance, the claim of "healing without antibiotics" (SO4) requires a	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Robust verification framework, ensuring comparable efficacy to conventional approaches, particularly in high-risk humanitarian contexts
Predictive models	The integration of AI predictive tools requires structured approaches to ensuring interpretability and accessibility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sequential validation protocols • Dataset provenance tracking: comprehensive data lineage documentation systems that record the origination, transformation, and utilisation of all data incorporated into predictive models • Meta-analytical calibration: weighted meta-analytical techniques based on methodological robustness, sample size, and replicability metrics. • Model architecture documentation: including network architectures, feature importance rankings, and decision boundaries.

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interpretability enhancement techniques: Integration of model-agnostic interpretation methods; e.g., SHAP (SHapley Additive exPlanations⁴) values to render complex algorithmic decisions comprehensible to non-specialist stakeholders.
Access and equality	The implementation in humanitarian contexts might reproduce North-South technological dependency dynamics.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Multi-stakeholder advisory consortium: Formation of a formally constituted governance body with designated representation from healthcare practitioners in humanitarian contexts, patient advocates, and local institutional partners with voting authority on key development decisions • Implementation of context-sensitive assessment protocols that can be calibrated to diverse deployment environments, recognising the limitations of standardised testing approaches • Implementation of a cyclical feedback mechanism whereby initial prototypes undergo sequential refinement through structured feedback from practitioners and recipients in simulated and actual deployment contexts. • Development of standardised protocols for evaluating the cultural acceptability of wound care approaches in diverse deployment contexts
	Effective knowledge transfer requires structured approaches that emphasise local capacity development:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Articulation of staged knowledge transfer pathways that identify prerequisite skills, intermediate competencies, and advanced capabilities required for local ownership of the technology

8.8. Ethical review processes

ANIPH employs a multi-layered ethical review framework designed to ensure comprehensive ethical oversight throughout the project lifecycle. This framework integrates internal governance structures with external expertise and continuous monitoring mechanisms to identify, assess, and mitigate potential ethical challenges proactively.

8.8.1. Internal ethics committees

The project operates with a dedicated internal ethics committee comprising representatives from each consortium partner, ensuring cross-disciplinary expertise across biotechnology, social sciences, and humanitarian ethics. This committee meets quarterly to review research protocols, assess data protection measures, and address emerging ethical concerns. The committee's responsibilities include maintaining ethical compliance logs, coordinating with work package leaders on sensitive activities (particularly tasks involving human subjects in 5.2 and 5.3), and developing responsive guidance for ethical dilemmas encountered during project implementation.

8.8.2. External ethics approvals

ANIPH maintains external ethical oversight through periodic consultations with the appointed external ethics advisor and submission of protocols to relevant national ethics boards where required. Prior to commencing any activities involving human participants, data collection, or AI systems development, proposals undergo rigorous external review. External approvals are

⁴ <https://datascientest.com/en/shap-what-is-it>

particularly crucial for studies involving wound dressing testing and stakeholder engagement in humanitarian contexts. All external ethics opinions are integrated into the project's decision-making processes and documented for accountability and transparency.

8.8.3. Ongoing ethical monitoring

Continuous ethical monitoring forms the backbone of ANIPH's ethical governance, featuring regular assessments aligned with key project milestones. This includes bi-annual comprehensive ethical audits, focused reviews during critical tasks, and responsive evaluations triggered by unexpected ethical issues. The monitoring system employs a combination of quantitative metrics (compliance indicators, informed consent completion rates, data protection measures) and qualitative assessments (stakeholder feedback, ethical culture indicators). All findings feed into iterative improvement processes, with mandatory reporting to both the consortium and the European Commission at designated intervals.

9. Conclusions

The ANIPH Data Management Plan establishes a comprehensive framework for ethical data governance throughout the project's PHA value chain development. This preliminary plan demonstrates commitment to the highest standards of data protection, research integrity, and responsible innovation whilst supporting the creation of biodegradable wound dressings and recyclable water barrier packaging.

The implementation of FAIR principles and GDPR-compliant data security frameworks ensures appropriate protection of sensitive information, throughout the research lifecycle.

Moreover, the extensive ethical framework addresses interdisciplinary challenges from AI transparency and EU AI Act compliance to human tissue research protocols, whilst RRI principles ensure societal impact encompasses sustainability and inclusivity goals beyond technological advancement. Also, structured resource allocation, defined responsibilities, comprehensive data breach protocols, and ongoing ethical monitoring provide the operational foundation for effective implementation and proactive risk management.

As this preliminary plan evolves through interim and final iterations (D.1.3 and D.7.1), it will adapt to emerging challenges whilst maintaining flexibility to support innovative research outcomes.

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11. Annex A. Consent form

Informed Consent Form – OPTION 1

Project acronym	ANIPH
Project full name	Avoiding the Negative Impacts produced by Plastic materials in Humanitarian contexts
Project partner	
Project duration	48 MONTHS
Funding and grant agreement	HORIZON EU - 101181943

INTRODUCTION

As part of ANIPH project, videos, audios and photographs may be recorded during the meetings and related activities such as workshops and events, aimed at project documentation, promotional activities and other related purposes.

The collected data will be used for research and project purposes only and always while protecting the identity of participants. Wherever possible, images or recordings will be anonymized or used in a way that does not disclose identifiable personal information unless explicit permission is provided

This documentation will be collected to document and promote the work carried out, showcasing the project's progress, share the results with the ANIPH community. The photos and videos may appear in reports, presentations, website, social media and other promotional materials, and educational resources.

The ANIPH project is committed to upholding the highest ethical standards in all activities, in particular: respect for autonomy, confidentiality, non-discrimination, transparency and data protection compliance.

USE OF IMAGES/RECORDINGS

- I understand that the images/recordings may be used for project documentation, educational content, promotional activities, and other related purposes.
- I agree that these images/recordings may be used without any further approval from me.

Duration of Consent

- This consent is valid indefinitely for project-related activities unless revoked in writing.
- Revocation will apply to future use of your images/recordings but cannot retroactively affect materials already published or disseminated.

No Compensation

- I understand that I will not receive any monetary compensation for my participation or for the use of images/recordings.

Revocation of Consent

- I understand that I may revoke this consent at any time by providing written notice to the project coordinator (CETEC).

Rights and Ownership

- I understand that the ANIPH project and its affiliates will own the rights to these images/recordings and may use them in any lawful and project-related manner, such as in reports, educational resources, promotional materials, or social media posts

Voluntary Participation

- My agreement to participate and allow photography/recording is completely voluntary, and I am free to withdraw my consent at any time.

Release of Liability

- I release the ANIPH project, its coordinators, and affiliates from any claims, damages, or liability arising from the use of my image/voice/likeness.

I, _____, hereby agree to be photographed and/or recorded as part of the ANIPH project activities

Participant's Information:

Name: _____

Signature: _____

Date: _____

I have received a copy of this agreement. This consent form is made pursuant to the relevant national, European data protection laws and regulations and personal data treatment obligations.

Informed Consent Form – OPTION 2

Responsible: ICONS, as Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication manager, will produce a set of communications resources and materials for the ANIPH project.

Purpose: we would like to share your names, entity affiliation, pictures and videos in our communications to increase visibility and impact. It helps to demonstrate the results, progress and advances that our work is making.

Legitimation: Processing and use of data necessary for the professional activity legitimised by the EU General Data Protection Regulation*.

Destinatory and duration: By accepting this form, you permit us to use your data/visual material in our open communications for the project's duration (in principle, planned for the next 48 months, from 1st January 2025 to 30th June 2027) and for as long as the project website and communication

channels remain active after the project ends (min. 1 year). Thank you for being so helpful!

Full name	
Job position	
Institution	
Country	
Email	

What will the data/visual material be used for?

The consent will allow the publication in the following sources:

- **Presentations:** ANIPH internal and external presentations
- **Websites and communications tools:** ANIPH website and/or intranet
- **Social media:** ANIPH social media pages [Twitter, LinkedIn, Youtube or similar]
- **Publications:** ANIPH leaflets, posters, roll-ups, videos, newsletters and other marketing materials
- **Print and online media:** National, regional and local papers; magazines and news sites
- **Television and radio:** National and regional television; national, regional and local radio

Can I remain anonymous?

Please tick this box if you do NOT want to be featured in imagery or video footage

Are there any identifying features/sources you do NOT want to be included in our communications work?

Please let us know if there are any ways in which you do NOT wish to be represented or described:

Consent agreement:

Please sign this form to show your agreement to permit your data to be used by ANIPH consortium for the above purposes. The permission can be revoked and you have the right to withdraw consent at any time.

Signature:

Date:

**General Data Protection Regulation: The information provided here will only be used to contact you about sharing your data and materials in our communications work. We will not circulate the details registered on this form to any other organisation without your permission. Furthermore, we will not store your data for longer than the duration of the project implementation. Find additional information in <https://gdpr.eu>*

